

TIMBERHAUS

D6.3: Analysis of local cultural traditions, crafts and design languages in partner cities

WP6

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Summary

This deliverable analyses local cultural traditions, crafts, and design languages in the three TIMBERHAUS partner cities-Baia Mare, Berlin, and Siena-through a combined approach of soft desk research and stakeholder perceptions. The objective is to build a place-based understanding of construction practices, material use, and woodworking traditions across urban and rural contexts, and to assess how these are preserved, transformed, or reinterpreted today.

The findings show that construction practices and material use are strongly shaped by territorial conditions, including the availability of natural resources, historical development patterns, and socio-economic transformations. Timber plays different roles across the three contexts: it remains a primary structural and cultural material in the rural areas of Baia Mare and Brandenburg, has historically been secondary but is re-emerging through innovation in Berlin, and maintains a complementary role within predominantly masonry-based systems in Siena.

At the same time, traditional crafts and woodworking practices continue to represent an important component of local identity, although their continuity is uneven and often challenged by industrialized construction, changing cultural perceptions, and limited transmission of skills.

By combining desk-based analysis with stakeholder perspectives, the report highlights both shared and context-specific dynamics, including the relationship between urban and rural systems, the evolution of construction techniques, and the current barriers and opportunities for wood use. These insights contribute to the comparative assessment and support the definition of culturally grounded and locally adapted approaches for future TIMBERHAUS co-creation sessions and pilot activities.

This deliverable is structured into a series of interconnected chapters that together provide a comprehensive analysis of local cultural traditions, crafts, and design languages in the three TIMBERHAUS partner cities-Baia Mare, Berlin, and Siena-across both urban and rural contexts.

Chapter 1. Introduction outlines the scope and objectives of the deliverable, focusing on the identification and analysis of local construction practices, woodworking traditions, and culturally embedded design languages. It also defines the role of the deliverable within the broader TIMBERHAUS project and its contribution to subsequent tasks and activities

Chapter 2. Methodology presents the framework of the study, structured around three main components: (i) soft desk research, (ii) stakeholder perceptions, and (iii) comparative assessment between partner cities. It explains the research questions, data sources, and analytical dimensions, including spatial form, building typologies and materials, cultural and identity-related elements, and transformations over time.

Chapter 3. Soft desk research provides a detailed, place-based analysis for each partner city (Baia Mare, Berlin, Siena), covering both urban and rural areas. The chapter examines settlement structures, construction practices, material use-particularly timber in relation to local resources-traditional woodworking techniques, and the evolution of these systems over time, based on policy documents, literature, and territorial observations.

Chapter 4. TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey presents the results of the stakeholder questionnaire conducted in each partner city, targeting actors from the construction and design

sector and heritage and crafts. It captures perceptions on current construction practices, wood use in urban and rural contexts, the role and continuity of traditional crafts, and the main barriers and opportunities identified by local stakeholders.

Chapter 5. Comparative assessment consolidates the findings from both the soft desk research and stakeholder survey into a synthesis and comparative analysis across the three cities and their urban and rural contexts. It highlights key similarities and differences in construction systems, material use, and cultural practices, as well as gaps between identified potential and stakeholder perceptions.

Chapter 6. Reference list compiles all sources used throughout the analysis, including policy documents, academic literature, and other relevant materials supporting the research.

Figure 1 TIMBERHAUS Partner Cities

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope of the deliverable

Identify and analyse the Local Cultural Traditions, Crafts and Design Languages in Partner Cities:

- Identify and collect perceptions on urban and rural construction practices, wood and cultural traditions of local crafts and design languages in Partner Cities;
- Lay the groundwork for urban–rural exchanges on wood construction methods, techniques, and “ways of building” between local stakeholders in Partner Cities;
- Inform the cultural dimension of the decarbonization strategies for buildings, the city action plans and roadmaps - with grounded qualitative insights and place-based, culturally-aware actions that can activate existing value chains

1.2. Relation to other TIMBERHAUS activities

D6.3 is complementary with/relies on the knowledge developed in other tasks and deliverables such as:

- Task 2.2 Historic and cultural design traditions of local crafts and design languages. This deliverable will provide insights into the specific cultural, architectural and building contexts of the three partner cities and their regions supporting thus D2.2 Analysis of local and regional cultural traditions, crafts and design languages within wood construction in Europe;
- Task 2.3 Design blueprints for multi-storey wood buildings, that will take into consideration adaptability for localised expression of/use of historic and cultural traditions, crafts and design languages. This deliverable will provide insights into the specific cultural, architectural and building contexts of the three partner cities and their regions for the development of the blueprints;
- Task 3.2 Demonstration of developed design principles and wood building blueprints through digital pilot projects.

Short-term and long-term perspective

The research scope of this deliverable is considering both short-term and long-term perspectives, linking analytical work with future-oriented implications for cities.

In the **short term**, the focus is on building a grounded understanding of local contexts in the partner cities. This involves identifying, collecting, and analysing perceptions related to wood use, as well as the cultural traditions of local crafts and design languages. In parallel, the research aim to support exchanges and dialogue between stakeholders, with a particular focus on urban–rural construction methods, techniques, and “ways of building” across the partner cities within the WP6 co-creation activities. These activities will contribute to a shared knowledge base that connects local practices with contemporary construction challenges.

In the **long term**, the insights generated through this research aim to inform broader strategic directions at city level. First, they can contribute to integrating cultural and local identity dimensions into decarbonisation strategies for buildings and urban action plans (WP7), through grounded, place-based approaches that can activate existing local value chains. Second, the findings can support the development of planning approaches that reconnect design with natural systems, positioning wood as a material that links climate action, cultural values, and spatial practices. Third, the research helps identify strategic areas where heritage-based and traditional construction practices can inform and support more innovative construction approaches and future policy agendas.

2. Methodology

The current deliverable is composed by three interconnected elements, leading to a better understanding of the state-of-play at Pilot City level:

- A. Soft desk research
- B. Local stakeholders perceptions
- C. Comparative assessment between partner cities

Figure 2 D6.3 Research components and methodology

The qualitative and place-based cultural insights gathered through these components will help contextualize the socio-cultural dimension of TIMBERHAUS pilot interventions. The aim is to inform the development of culturally-rooted digital pilot projects, strengthen urban-rural linkages, and support NEB-inspired actions through heritage-based design languages and local traditions in wood construction.

This report will achieve its goals through the following components:

(A) Soft Desk Research

Aim: Build a contextual general baseline for each partner city. Mapping and analysing (i) urban and rural development and building practices and (ii) woodworking and timber construction practices as expressions of local cultural identity across the three Partner cities.

Research questions:

- What construction practices, techniques, design languages, and materials shaped/define the urban and rural development in each partner city?

- What are the historic and contemporary woodworking construction practices, traditions and crafts, in each partner city, and if/how are they preserved, adapted, or transmitted today?

The analysis draws from different local sources such as local cultural and touristic development strategies and policy documents, heritage and planning studies, academic literature and own territorial observations to provide general insights into:

- **Spatial and urban/rural form:** analysis of traditional settlement patterns in rural and urban contexts, the morphology of neighborhoods, streets, and blocks, and the ways in which rural areas influence and feed into the development and functioning of the city.
- **Building typologies, techniques and materials:** typical buildings in urban and rural areas (e.g., farmhouses, rural cottages, townhouses, community buildings); main materials used (stone, timber, clay, etc.) and how they reflect environmental and contextual conditions (e.g. existing resources on the territory-forests);
- **Cultural and symbolic/ identity elements:** role of cultural identity in shaping design and building practices (craftsmanship, ornamentation); how traditions, crafts and embedded meanings influence design;
- **Transformations over time:** shifts in construction practices due to socio-economic or political changes, current preservation or adaptation trends.

(B) Stakeholder Perceptions

This component aims to gather and reflect the perspectives of local stakeholders on wood and traditional crafts, and culturally embedded design languages in both urban and rural areas. It will further support knowledge exchange and co-creation activities with the local stakeholders, enabling a deeper understanding of how traditional woodworking practices can inform contemporary construction and sustainability approaches.

TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

Tool aiming to collect perceptions on local historical and cultural traditions of crafts and design languages in urban and rural areas and wood use, with a particular focus on how these are understood, valued, and applied by local stakeholders within each of the three Partner cities: Berlin (Germany), Baia Mare (Romania), and Siena (Italy).

Targeted stakeholder groups at local and regional (rural) levels:

- Heritage and Crafts – craftsmen, artisans, heritage experts, cultural institutions, craft schools
- Construction and Design – architects, engineers, builders, urban planner, professional associations

The questionnaire collects information on: Local urban and rural construction practices, Wood use in local urban and rural construction, Local urban and rural historic construction practices and Local historic crafts.

(C) Comparative assessment

This final component consolidates the findings from the 2 analysis research components, desk-based analysis and stakeholder questionnaires, into a coherent synthesis per Partner city. It enables a comparative perspective across the three contexts (Berlin, Baia Mare, Siena) both from a urban and regional perspective and outlines key unique and shared features across the three context

3. Soft desk research

3.1. Baia Mare, Romania

Baia Mare (108.759 inhabitants in 2021¹) is a medium-sized city in northwestern Romania, located in a mountainous basin in Maramureş County, with a strong historical identity shaped by mining, culture, and its **proximity to natural landscapes**.

Based on the Eurostat NUTS 3 classification², Maramureş county (RO114) is a **predominantly rural region**, characterized by low population density and a high share of villages and small settlements.

Although it includes urban centers such as Baia Mare, the county remains largely structured by rural landscapes and activities, with urban areas playing a secondary role. This means that the majority of its territory is characterized by **low population density, dispersed settlements, and dependence on rural economic activities**.

Figure 3 Romania – NUTS 3 level Urban Rural typology

Figure 4 (below) Baia Mare county in european and national context. Source: Cultural development strategy of Baia Mare municipality 2015-2030

România - NUTS level 3

Figure 5 Baia Mare municipality within the Maramureş county and Baia Mare Metropolitan Area. Source: Cultural development strategy of Baia Mare municipality 2015-2030

¹ National Institute of Statistics (INS)

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/345175/20613256/romania-nuts-2024-level-3.png/f4f678ec-06b2-2178-6e54-7374da6f5db1?t=1734449350967>

Urban area

Baia Mare lies in a **depression surrounded by hills and mountains**, at the foothills of the Gutâi Mountains, which are part of the Eastern Carpathians. This setting gives the city a strong connection to both mountainous landscapes and accessible valleys. It is situated **along the Săsar River**, which crosses the city and contributes to its historical development as a mining and trade center.

Baia Mare municipality presents a layered urban structure. The historic core includes street grids and brick courtyard buildings. Socialist-era expansion brought prefabricated housing blocks and industrial platforms, based on centralised planning principles. Post-1990 development trends led to urban sprawl, informal construction, and mixed-use fragmentation (Municipiul Baia Mare, n.d.). Despite its scale, Baia Mare functions as a regional service hub for surrounding rural communes, with high levels of commuting and interdependence, though these links are not fully supported by integrated territorial planning (Consiliul Judeţean Maramureş, 2021-2027).

Figure 6 Aerial view of Baia Mare city. Source: romaniadategeografice.net³

Figure 7 Urban fabric Baia Mare city. Source: Google Earth

Figure 8 Urban tissue typologies in Baia Mare city. Source: Google Earth

³ <https://romaniadategeografice.net/unitati-admin-teritoriale/municipii/municipii-b/baia-mare/>

Historic core: Compact historic center characterized by an irregular street network, dense plots, and buildings aligned to the street, reflecting pre-modern urban morphology.

Residential area (individual housing): Low-density residential neighborhood with detached/semi-detached houses, gardens, and a street pattern adapted to the natural topography and river course.

Planned residential / mixed urban fabric: Intermediate urban fabric combining individual housing and collective dwellings, with a more regular street network and defined urban blocks.

Socialist housing estates: Large-scale residential development with apartment blocks arranged in superblocks, characterized by repetitive layouts and open spaces between buildings and linear mixed-used corridors on the main streets.

Industrial and logistic area : Industrial platform with large buildings, functional layouts, and strong dependence on transport infrastructure, forming a distinct urban zone.

Figure 9 Building typologies in Baia Mare. Source: Google Street View

1) Detached housing; 2) Socialist housing estates; 3) Post-socialist developments; 4) Historic perimeter blocks; 5) Industrial and logistic ; 6) Linear mixed-use corridors

Baia Mare's urban fabric is characterized by a heterogeneous mix of historical and modern structures, shaped by successive waves of development throughout the 20th and 21st centuries. The central area retains a compact, traditional street grid, with buildings aligned to the street edge and plots dating back to the Austro-Hungarian period or earlier. This includes preserved typologies such as **courtyard houses, administrative palaces, and mixed-use urban blocks**, many of which hold heritage value.

Outside the historic core, the fabric transitions into linear **mixed-use corridors** along main arterial roads, with mid-rise blocks (typically 2–4 stories) and retail or service functions at ground level. These areas reflect urban renewal processes from the socialist period and early post-socialist transition.

Alongside these, the urban periphery includes **modernist housing estates from the communist era**, characterized by prefabricated apartment blocks, relatively high building density, and unevenly

defined public spaces. These zones reflect industrial-era expansion and show limited integration into the pre-existing urban structure.

Recent development trends indicate increasing infill construction, functional re-zoning, and diversified uses including cultural, religious, touristic, and financial services. The result is a layered yet increasingly fragmented urban fabric, where formal planning frameworks coexist with spontaneous and adaptive re-use.

While **brick and reinforced concrete prevail in contemporary construction, timber maintains symbolic and aesthetic value, especially in museum design, tourist buildings, and other culturally significant projects.** Efforts to preserve wooden heritage are carried forward through cultural institutions and architectural restoration programs, seeking to preserve traditional forms while adapting them for present-day uses.

Rural area

Figure 10 The four ethnographic regions of Maramureș County. Source: valeachioarului.ro

The county of Maramureș is traditionally divided into four main ethnographic regions - historically and culturally distinct “lands,” each with its own traditions, lifestyles and identities.

The ethnographic regions of Maramureș display distinct cultural and spatial identities, ranging from the iconic and symbolically strong Maramureș Land, to the culturally cohesive and ritual-rich Lăpușului Land, the hybrid and transitional Chioarului Land (where Baia Mare is located) with greater diversity but lower coherence, and the more functional, agrarian Codrului Land, characterized by reduced architectural expressiveness and symbolic identity.

Maramureș Land (Țara Maramureșului)

- The core and most emblematic area, most coherent and best-preserved traditional system
- Represents the strongest continuity of vernacular architecture and social structures
- Settlements typically linear along valleys (Iza, Vișeu), with highly consistent spatial organization
- Architecture dominated by: monumental wooden gates, tall wooden churches (UNESCO-listed), highly refined wood craftsmanship
- Houses and annexes form well-structured households, reflecting a stable agro-pastoral system
- Strong preservation of: traditional costumes, customs and rituals, community structures

Lăpușului Land (Țara Lăpușului)

- A distinct and cohesive cultural area centered around Târgu Lăpuș
- Rich in rituals, festivals, and oral traditions
- Notable for wooden architecture (e.g. Rogoz church)
- Strong sense of local identity

Chioarului Land (Țara Chioarului) – where Baia Mare city is located

- Located around Șomcuta Mare
- A transition zone between Maramureș and Transylvania

- Displays mixed cultural influences
- Traditions are less uniformly preserved compared to the northern areas

Codrului Land (Țara Codrului)

- Extends beyond Maramureș into neighboring counties (e.g Satu Mare, Sălaj)
- Characterized by a more agrarian lifestyle
- Distinct but somewhat less visually iconic cultural expressions
- Specific folk costume and customs tied to rural life

Cultural identity in Maramureș is expressed through **vernacular architecture, local crafts, and traditional occupations, including agriculture, animal husbandry, woodworking, and textile production**. The presence of wooden churches and traditional household structures reflects a strong continuity of local craftsmanship, while practices such as weaving, sewing, and other artisanal activities remain part of the intangible cultural heritage, although increasingly limited to older generations.

Traditional crafts in Maramureș villages are closely linked to the use and processing of local resources, particularly wood. Initially practiced at the household level, these activities later evolved into more specialized forms. Woodworking plays a central role, including primary processing techniques such as cutting, splitting, and shaping timber for construction elements (houses, annexes, gates) as well as for smaller objects like furniture, tools, and household items.

Alongside woodworking, other important crafts include wood carving, textile production (weaving and sewing), basketry, and blacksmithing, used for producing wheels, sledges, ploughs, and horseshoes. Activities such as beekeeping and fruit growing are also part of this traditional system. Pottery has been as well an essential component of the material culture in Maramureș, traditionally practiced in numerous localities. Today, the center in Săcel keeps this tradition alive, distinguished by archaic techniques such as red firing and polishing with stone. These crafts are embedded in a broader structure of occupations based on agriculture, animal husbandry, and forestry, contributing to the self-sufficiency of rural households. Today, while still present in rural areas, many of these practices are in gradual decline, with some being reoriented towards tourism and the promotion of local products.

Figure 11 Wood carving. Source: eziarultau.ro⁴

⁴ <https://eziarultau.ro/featured/cat-ii-maramuresu-sunt-ioan-petric-sunt-unul-dintre-mesterii-populari-din-satul-breb>

Figure 12 (upper right) Pottery. Mr. Burnar Tanase inherited from his father (Tanase Cocean) the workshop and the passion of giving shape to the clay. Source: acasalaromani.ro⁵

Figure 13 Maramureş crafts and traditions (Right column) 2) Traditional food preparation, 3) Traditional straw hat, 4) Traditional dance and folk costumes. Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Chioarului

Figure 14 Maramureş crafts and traditions (left column). Source: OAR, Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramures Land. 1) *Processing of dranița*, 2) *Raising animals in households*, 3) *Woman spinning yarn while seated on a bench*, 4) *Tourists practicing mountain biking*, 5) *Mowing grass*.

⁵ <https://acasalaromani.ro/tanase-burnar/>

Figure 15 “The harmony between the natural landscape and the built landscape of the villages of Maramureş” Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramures Land

Rural areas in Maramureş, particularly in Chioarului Land, are characterized by a diverse range of settlement typologies shaped by a predominantly hilly landscape and a network of valleys that structure circulation and habitation patterns. Villages developed along these natural corridors and trade routes, resulting in linear settlements along roads and valleys, dispersed hillside dwellings, and compact village clusters.

Figure 16 Rural settlements typologies in Maramureş, Chioarului Land. Source: Google Earth

- 1) settlement with densely grouped households – Finteşu Mare village
- 2) dispersed and isolated settlement - Preluca Veche village
- 3) compact (clustered) settlement- Săsar village
- 4) settlement developed along the main road - Satulung commune
- 5) isolated valley settlement - Handalul Ilbei village ⁶

⁶ Order of Architects of Romania - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Cioarului Land.

The rural built environment reflects a strong integration between natural and constructed landscapes, with traditional households organized as **agro-pastoral units**. These include the main dwelling and a series of annexes, arranged according to functional needs and terrain conditions. The spatial organization often evolves from a more compact nucleus to dispersed peripheral structures, with isolated houses marking the transition to surrounding agricultural land.

Figure 17 Street elevation in Botiza (left), 1968. DITACP/UAIIM survey archive. Source: Order of Architects of Romania - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramureș Land.

Figure 18 Elements of the traditional Maramureș household (right) – the dwelling house and outbuildings: the barn, grain storage (coleşna), pigsty, poultry coop, and well. Household in Oncești, 1968. DITACP/UAIIM survey archive. Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramureș Land.

The characteristic image of the area has been best preserved especially in isolated zones, where valley settlements experienced a more accentuated development, although this has led in some cases to a weakening of traditional identity.

Construction techniques are based on the use of locally available materials, particularly wood, earth, and stone, reflecting both environmental conditions and resource availability. Timber is widely used for structural elements and detailing, while earth-based materials (such as clay) are employed for wall infill and finishes. Stone is typically used for foundations. Roofs are generally steep and adapted to climatic conditions, contributing to the coherent visual identity of the area.

The architectural expression is defined by simplicity, functional clarity, and discreet decorative elements, with buildings adapted to both topography and economic activities, especially agriculture and animal husbandry.⁷

Woodworking and timber construction

The wooden architecture of Maramureș reflects a vernacular architecture based almost exclusively on locally available resources. **Oak, fir, and spruce serve as primary structural materials, while straw and clay are used for roofing and insulation, and stone for foundations (OAR, 2021).**

The rural architectural heritage is defined by three main components: wooden houses, wooden gates, and wooden churches. Structures from the 17th and 18th centuries still stand

⁷ Order of Architects of Romania - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Chioarului Land.

today, often alongside newer constructions built in the same traditional style. Houses in Lăpuşului and Chioarului Lands follow log or beam construction, sealed with clay and capped by steep shingled roofs, ensuring resilience against harsh climatic conditions.

A defining feature of this tradition is the **Blockbau technique**, where manually hewn logs are stacked horizontally and joined at the corners with dovetail joints, steps joints, or the archaic Romanian notch (cheotoare). These joinery methods provide stability without the use of metal fasteners, relying instead on wooden pegs and precision craftsmanship (Iuga, 2014). Tool marks left by axes or adzes remain visible, imbuing the structures with a sense of authenticity and cultural continuity. From the 19th century onward, this method was gradually complemented or replaced by the “German notch,” inspired by Central European carpentry and commonly associated with the Blockbau system. These joining techniques not only ensure the durability of the construction but also contribute to the distinctive aesthetic of vernacular wooden architecture in Maramureş.⁸

Wooden churches

Figure 19 Wooden churches from Maramureş. a) Săpânța; b) Oncești; c) Șurdești; d) Budești; e) Basic plans of different wooden churches. Source: Researchgate.net - Analysis of Joints and Ornaments of The Wooden Churches Structures in Maramureş County⁹

⁸ *The wooden churches of Maramureş – elements of timber civilization in Romania.* Curtu, I., Stanciu, M.D., Floroiu, M., & Coman, M. (2011).

⁹ <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283571780> Analysis of Joints and Ornaments of The Wooden Churches Structures in Maramures County

The **joining techniques** reaches its most iconic form in the **UNESCO-recognized wooden churches** of Maramureş. These buildings employ sophisticated timber joints, steep shingled spires, and interior vaults assembled from planks fixed with loops and nails. Beyond their structural ingenuity, these churches embody **symbolic cosmology**: the nave represents the sky, and the chancel is covered by a polygonal dome, reflecting the spiritual and cultural identity of the region (Ilieş et al., 2018).

Out of the 105 surviving structures of this kind in the region, eight have been inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List, selected for their outstanding representation of vernacular religious wooden architecture.

Such structures not only meet functional and environmental requirements but also preserve regional identity within the wider narrative of sustainable construction.

Figure 20 Spruce wooden beams, joined at the corners in a "dovetail" pattern (upper right) Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramureş Land

Figure 21 Blockbau system . The wooden churches of Maramureş – elements of timber civilization in Romania. Curtu, I., Stanciu, M.D., Floroiu, M., & Coman, M. (2011)

Figure 22 a)Types of square-ended joints from the walls construction, b) the steps joints. Source: The wooden churches of Maramureş – elements of timber civilization in Romania

Ornamental motifs in Maramureş are found in wood carvings on doors, walls, and pillars, carrying spiritual meanings rooted in Christian-Orthodox beliefs and Romanian traditions.

The most common symbols include the tree of life, the cross, the sun, the wheel, the crown, spiral (rope) patterns, as well as floral, animal, and astrological motifs. In addition, painted decorations use vivid colors to depict biblical scenes, with styles influenced by Byzantine culture and medieval Western traditions.¹⁰

The spread of Maramureş-style wooden churches beyond local borders reflects the enduring cultural identity and symbolic value of the region, which continues to influence heritage landscapes across the country.

¹⁰ Source: Curtu, I., Stanciu, M.D., Floroiu, M., & Coman, M. (2011). *The wooden churches of Maramureş – elements of timber civilization in Romania*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263363287>

Figure 23 Christian and pre-Christian ornaments carved in wood. Source: The wooden churches of Maramureş – elements of timber civilization in Romania¹¹

Figure 24 Maramureş Land. Location of wooden churches beyond the region. Source: Ilieş et al., What Future for the Land of the Wooden Civilisation?, 2018

Traditional wooden houses

Roofs are the defining element of traditional architecture in Chioarului Land, characterized by steep slopes (40–50°) and simple, stable volumes. Traditional coverings include thatch, shingles, and later tiles. Roofs are typically four-sided, sometimes enhanced with small elements like porches or dormer-like structures. Functional aspects dominate: wide eaves, lack of gutters, and simple ridge solutions adapted to local climate and materials.

Figure 25 Traditional roof structure. Source: Order of Architects of Romania - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramureşului Land

Walls are primarily made of timber structures filled with earth (wattle and daub), later partially replaced by brick. Finishes include clay plaster and limewash, often in light, monochrome tones. Construction systems are based on wooden frames (posts and beams), ensuring flexibility and durability. The use of natural materials and proper maintenance is essential for longevity.

Traditional **foundations** consist of dry stone masonry, using local materials, ensuring ventilation and protection against moisture for wooden structures. Proper construction and drainage are critical, as water infiltration can lead to structural degradation. Contemporary interventions recommend avoiding continuous concrete slabs and instead maintaining traditional solutions or integrating compatible systems, ensuring proper drainage and ventilation.

Joinery is generally simple and functional, made of wood. Windows are small, vertically proportioned, often double-leaf, with limited glazing area and simple frames. Doors are modest in size and design. Decorative elements are minimal, and traditional craftsmanship is encouraged over modern standardized solutions.

Façades are defined by horizontal and vertical elements, especially the porch (prisa/târnaţ), which creates a transitional space between interior and exterior, used for rest, storage, or household activities. The porch contributes significantly to the overall composition and silhouette of the house. Façades are typically plain, finished with lime-based coatings in light tones, and characterized by balanced proportions and a restrained use of decoration.

¹¹ <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263363287> The wooden churches of Maramures - elements of timber civilization in Romania

Figure 26 Types of târnaț according to planimetry (left). Types of târnaț after parapet (târnaț without parapet, târnaț with relative, târnaț with parapet) Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Lăpușului Land.

Figure 27 Richly decorated porch. Village Museum from Sighetu Marmăției. Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Maramureșului Land.

Figure 28 Târnaț Chioarului Land (bottom right) Source: OAR - Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Chioarului Land.

Households include a variety of functional **annexes** (barns, sheds, kitchens, storage structures), reflecting agro-pastoral activities. These structures are directly linked to the household economy and are proportionate to the social status and occupation of the family. Common elements include barns for hay and tools, animal shelters (stables, pigsties, poultry houses), summer kitchens, bread ovens, and storage buildings such as granaries (găbănaș). These annexes are often built from wood, earth, or a combination of materials, sometimes under the same roof as the house or grouped within the same courtyard, forming a coherent functional ensemble.

Unlike other ethnographic regions, **gates** in Chioarului Land are less monumental and more discreet, typically made of wood with simple geometric or anthropomorphic decorative motifs. Historically, gates were taller and more elaborate, but today they are often lower and more functional. **Fences** are also modest in height, made of wooden planks or vertical slats, marking property boundaries rather than acting as visual statements. Traditional systems have been gradually replaced by metal or prefabricated elements, which are discouraged, as they do not reflect local architectural specificity.¹²

Wooden gates

Cultural symbolism is strongly expressed through the **Maramureș gate — a monumental carved wooden entrance** that historically marked social status, being reserved for noble households, while other community members used simpler wooden barriers (“vraniță”). Today, it is recognized as a

¹² Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Țara Chioarului. Order of Architects of Romania https://oar.archi/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/ghid_de_arhitectura_tara_chioarului_pdf_1510849069.pdf

national cultural heritage symbol and a powerful marker of local and regional identity. Its intricate geometric and floral motifs reflect a high level of craftsmanship while also conveying belonging and cultural continuity.

With over 2,000 such gates inventoried by 2010, they remain defining features of the rural landscape, contributing to its distinct visual character and to the broader cultural richness of Europe. Although structurally vulnerable and requiring periodic restoration, these gates are widely valued as artistic elements rather than solely as heritage assets, reinforcing their dual role as functional and symbolic elements within Maramureș villages.

Figure 29 Old images with gates from Chiarului Land (upper right). Today dissapered. Architectural guide for fitting into the local specifics of the rural environment of Țara Chioarului. OAR

Figure 30 Gate from Maramureș. Source_Google photos

The symbolic significance of wooden gates as well as vernacular carpentry goes beyond the rural areas, influencing preservation policies in Baia Mare's urban core and shaping the architectural style of its cultural insitutions. However, urban expansion and the rising land values pose as a threaten to some historic wooden structures, leading to a gradual loss of traditional streetscapes. This tension between economic development and heritage preservation has prompted initiatives such as the 'Mara-Gutâi Local Action Group', which combines restoration efforts with digital tools-such as virtual tours under the 'Biserici de

Lemn'. 'Tururi Virtuale' project-to broaden public engagement. In this way, timber in Maramureș architecture embodies a living tradition, negotiating between historic authenticity and modern reinterpretation while remaining a central component of the region's identity.¹³

Transformations over time

The evolution of construction practices in Maramureș, including Baia Mare and its surrounding areas, reflects a series of socio-economic and political shifts structured across distinct periods.

In the 1990s, following the fall of the communist regime, both urban and rural areas experienced significant disruption. The transition to a market economy led to the privatization of land and changes in rural land management, contributing to temporary rural depopulation and reduced maintenance of traditional timber buildings. At the same time, policies from this period aggravated social challenges, leading to demographic decline, population ageing, and increased migration. Changes in property regimes-from public to private and co-owned forest resources-facilitated deforestation while making legally regulated wood harvesting more difficult and expensive, directly affecting the use of timber in construction.

During the 2000–2009 period, the built environment increasingly reflected the effects of mobility and economic change. Labour migration, both within Romania (before 1990) and towards Western Europe (after 2000), contributed to the import of new architectural styles. As a result, the built

¹³ https://oar.archi/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/ghid_de_arhitectura_tara_lapusului_pdf_1510849209.pdf

landscape evolved into a mix of traditional buildings in wood and brick and newer constructions, often developed without strong reference to local architectural identity. In parallel, Baia Mare and its surrounding areas experienced changes in housing patterns, with new developments supported by income from abroad, contributing to a diversification of building types and construction approaches.

Between 2010 and 2016, preservation and adaptation trends became more visible. Efforts focused particularly on the protection and promotion of Maramureș's wooden churches, some of which are UNESCO World Heritage sites, encouraging restoration projects and heritage tourism, although implementation remained limited. At the same time, strategies highlighted the need to restore other historic buildings, including cultural and civic structures, some of which remain in poor condition.

More recently, planning and development trends in Baia Mare reflect a shift towards more compact and sustainable urban growth. While urban expansion has occurred, local strategies emphasize densification within existing boundaries in order to prevent uncontrolled suburban growth, alongside the reuse of abandoned industrial platforms and the improvement of infrastructure. However, many cities, including Baia Mare, continue to face demographic decline, raising concerns about the long-term costs of expanding urban areas. In this context, outdated urban plans (PUGs) limit the capacity to regulate development effectively, particularly in rapidly changing peri-urban zones (Strategia de Dezvoltare Durabilă a Județului Maramureș, 2021–2027).

Across the region, shifting patterns between urban and rural living are also evident. While many residents have migrated outward, there is also a visible trend of relocation from urban areas such as Baia Mare to surrounding rural communes, driven by lower living costs, better environmental conditions, and access to larger plots. This has led to residential growth in peri-urban areas and changing land-use patterns, reflecting a dual dynamic of urban decline and rural expansion (INSSE, 2015–2023).

Overall, these transformations highlight a dual trajectory in the built environment: on the one hand, efforts to preserve and revalorize cultural heritage, and on the other, the emergence of new construction practices and housing models. The result is a hybrid landscape, where traditional and modern elements coexist, reflecting both continuity and change.

The **timber construction heritage** of Maramureș is currently navigating a complex transition. While wooden houses, gates, and churches have long defined the region's cultural identity, modernization pressures and changing socio-economic conditions are reshaping how these structures are valued, built, and preserved. Traditional timber buildings are increasingly replaced by modern houses that favor urban-style comfort and materials like concrete and plasterboard, often disregarding local architectural language. This shift is especially visible in suburban and peripheral areas, where vernacular identity is at risk of disappearance.¹⁴

Still, pockets of resistance and renewal exist. In villages like Breb, cultural and tourism projects are reviving traditional carpentry and rural aesthetics, using them in guesthouses, workshops, and architectural reinterpretations. Projects like *Casa din Vale* show how tourism can become a driver of reinterpretation, promoting wooden craftsmanship (e.g., carved gates, shingles, woven fences) while supporting economic development and preserving local skills.¹⁵

At the same time, wooden churches remain cultural landmarks, highly valued for their durability, symbolism, and spiritual meaning. While new ones are still being built (e.g., the Bârsana church), some older churches are being sold or dismantled due to maintenance costs or demographic decline.

¹⁴https://www.academia.edu/116297440/Mihai_D%C4%83ncu%C8%99_Obiceiuri_din_via%C8%9Ba_omului_%C3%AE_n_Maramures_I_Na%C8%99terea_%C8%99i_copii%C4%83ria_2009

¹⁵ <https://casadinvalebreb.ro/experiente-activitati/>

This reflects a broader tension: Maramureş is caught between the need to modernize and the importance of preserving identity through material culture.¹⁶

Ultimately, the region's timber legacy remains alive, but fragile—sustained by small-scale craftsmanship, tourism initiatives, and a few dedicated communities. Without stronger heritage protection policies or architectural education, the risk remains that this intangible cultural knowledge may erode, especially under the forces of real estate speculation and emigration.

The contrast between the idealized image of Maramureş – as a land of traditions and wooden architecture – and the current reality of its villages is increasingly striking.

Traditional buildings have been rapidly replaced by modern houses, often lacking identity, poorly integrated into the local context, and aesthetically unappealing. While the tourism sector showcases positive examples of vernacular reinterpretation, private homes tend to avoid traditional references, which are often associated by locals with poverty and discomfort.

The main causes of this transformation include easy access to modern construction materials, a desire for urban-style comfort, and the diminishing symbolic value of local architectural heritage.

¹⁶ <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263363287> The wooden churches of Maramures - elements of timber civilization in Romania

3.2. Berlin, Germany

Berlin (3,769,495 inhabitants in 2021) is the capital and largest city of Germany, located in northeastern Germany, with a strong urban identity shaped by its historical role as a political, economic, and cultural center, as well as by its complex 20th-century history.

It is administratively distinct as one of Germany's federal states, despite being among the smallest in terms of area, and is entirely surrounded by the state of Brandenburg, including its capital, Potsdam, located to the southwest.

According to the Eurostat NUTS 3 classification categorized based on the degree of urbanization Berlin-Brandenburg is **predominantly composed of intermediate and largely rural regions**, with Berlin (DE300) as the only predominantly urban area. This spatial structure reinforces the pattern of a dense urban core surrounded by extensive rural and semi-rural territories, with important implications for land-use planning, mobility networks, and resource distribution.

Deutschland (Ost) - NUTS level 3

eurostat

Administrative boundaries: © EuroGeographics © OpenStreetMap contributors © Turstat
Cartography: Eurostat — GISCO, 11/2024

Figure 31 Urban–Rural Typology of Berlin–Brandenburg (upper right), according to Eurostat NUTS Level 3 Regions

Figure 32 Berlin within Brandenburg region, Source: <https://blickgewinkelt.de/brandenburg/>

Urban area

Berlin's urban fabric is characterized by a **dense and highly structured** metropolitan layout with shaped by successive phases of expansion, industrialization, war destruction, and post-reunification redevelopment.

The spatial layout is defined by high-density zoning, transportation corridors and historic fragmentation between the East and the West part. The planning logic prioritised functional separation, resulting in uneven development between districts.

The **central area** combines historic street patterns with later planned interventions, forming a layered urban core with compact blocks, buildings aligned to the street, and a strong mix of residential, commercial, and institutional functions.

Areas such as Potsdamer Platz reflect more recent urban development, characterized by a modern, open grid pattern with wider streets and larger urban blocks. Buildings in these zones are typically **mid-to high-rise, with flat roofs and contemporary materials such as glass, steel, and concrete**, while green pockets and generous sidewalks provide spatial relief.

Outside the historic core, the city is largely defined by continuous **perimeter block developments (Blockrand)**, creating coherent urban neighborhoods with well-defined streets, inner courtyards, and relatively high density. These areas reflect systematic urban planning from the late 19th and early 20th centuries, as well as later reconstruction phases.

Alongside these, Berlin includes **large-scale housing estates developed during both the socialist (East Berlin) and modernist (West Berlin) periods**, characterized by apartment blocks arranged in open layouts, integrated green spaces, and supporting infrastructure. Compared to smaller cities, these areas are generally better connected to the overall urban structure.

Figure 33 Aerial view of Berlin city (upper right). Source: unsplash

Figure 34 Urban fabric Berlin. Source: Google Earth

Industrial and logistic areas, historically linked to manufacturing and transport infrastructure, are distributed across the city, often along rail corridors and waterways. Many of these areas are currently undergoing processes of regeneration and functional transformation, being integrated into mixed-use urban developments.

Figure 35 Urban tissue typologies in Berlin city. Source: Google Earth

Recent development trends emphasize **densification, infill construction, and the adaptive reuse of existing buildings and former industrial sites**. The result is a relatively coherent and continuous urban fabric, where historical layers, planned developments, and contemporary interventions are integrated within a strong metropolitan structure.

Berlin's **architecture** is a fragmented, multi-layered timeline, shifting from Prussian neoclassicism to industrial density, Bauhaus modernism, 20th-century devastation, and reunification-era experimentation. The city functions as a mosaic of styles, featuring 19th-century *Gründerzeit* blocks (Figure x), 1920s UNESCO-listed housing, socialist-era buildings, and post-1990 steel-and-glass structures, often coexisting in the same neighborhood.¹⁷

Key evolutionary stages of Berlin:

- **Prussian and Imperial Era** (19th Century): Defined by Neoclassicism (Karl Friedrich Schinkel) and the rapid, dense growth of *Gründerzeit* tenement buildings with hidden, often grim, rear courtyards.
- **Modernism and Bauhaus** (1920s): the city became a hub for the avant-garde (Bruno Taut, Walter Gropius). The city developed iconic housing estates (*Siedlungen*) like the Hufeisensiedlung (Horseshoe Estate), focusing on light, air, and functionalism, now UNESCO World Heritage sites.
- **Post-War Divided City** (1950s–1980s):
 - **West:** Focused on modernism and reconstructing the urban fabric, highlighted by the 1957 Interbau exhibition in the Hansaviertel.
 - **East:** Dominated by socialist classicism and industrial pre-fabricated panel buildings (*Plattenbau*), notably along Karl-Marx-Allee.
- **Reunification and Contemporary Era** (1990s–Present): A surge of iconic projects filling the "death strip" of the Berlin Wall, featuring critical reconstruction, glass-facade towers, and modern insertions like the Axel Springer Neubau.
- **Industrial Reutilization:** Former infrastructure, such as the E-Werk and Kindl brewery, has been repurposed into tech hubs, venues, and art spaces.

Iconic architectural landmarks includes: Brandenburg Gate (Neoclassical), Reichstag (Historicism with modern Norman Foster dome), Berliner Philharmonie (Organic modernism), Bauhaus Archive (Functionalist), Am Tacheles (Contemporary mixed-use). The city's evolution is heavily marked by "critical reconstruction," seeking a balance between preserving historical layouts and creating modern, functional spaces.¹⁸

¹⁷ <https://www.visitberlin.de/en/events-urban-development-berlin#:~:text=From%20the%20Middle%20Ages%20to%20the%20future:.for%20living%20and%20working%20in%20the%20city.>

¹⁸ <https://www.re-thinkingthefuture.com/city-and-architecture/a7250-architectural-development-of-berlin-germany/>

Figure 36 Hufeisensiedlung (Horseshoe Estate). Source:Wikipedia

Figure 37 Karl-Marx-Allee. Source:Wikipedia

Figure 38 Axel Springer Neubau. Source: obo.ae

Monumental architecture plays a central role in shaping cultural symbolism. The Prussian Stadtschloss, the East German Palast der Republik, and the reconstructed Humboldt Forum are notable examples of civic and palatial structures that reflect the evolution of Berlin's history through different shifts in politics. As noted by Bartmanski & Fuller (2018), such structures fall within a "logic of enchantment," where architectural form **reinforces political symbolism**, while engaging the public. The strategic use of sandstone and other durable materials in monumental facades demonstrates that buildings using such materials aim to convey performance.

Beyond monumental forms, Berlin's identity is also defined by its capacity to negotiate between erasure and remembrance. The city's landscape is defined by a mosaic of spaces shaped by history - former border zones, wartime ruins, and deindustrialised sites -now reimagined through memorials, adaptive reuse and cultural initiatives.

The Palast der Republik, built in East Berlin during the GDR period, illustrates how material choice shapes political and cultural narratives. While its structure was steel, concrete, and brick, its bronze-tinted glass façade contrasted with the symbolic permanence of stone in historic state buildings, signaling a modernist socialist identity rather than traditional authority.

Berlin's urban morphology combines a range of **residential typologies** – such as perimeter blocks row developments, multi-story housing, village cores, and large housing estates – each linked to specific historical phases and socio-economic contexts. These typologies define not only the architecture, but also the spatial structure of the city, influencing block patterns, street layouts and open space distribution. The morphological diversity reflects Berlin's layered urban development, from compact 19th century blocks to the post-war modernist estates and more recent sustainable housing initiatives.

Figure 39 Example of monumental civic architecture (bottom right) – Palast der Republik¹⁹

¹⁹ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/13604813.2018.1451100?needAccess=true>

The mix illustrates how changing political priorities, housing demands, and planning philosophies have shaped the city's physical form over time.

- **Perimeter blocks:** Mainly built 1870 to 1918, typically 4-6 stories, high density. Characteristic inner yards (varieties: built-up courtyards, closed, half-closed blocks)

- **Row development, open blocks:** Constructed between the 1920s and the 1970s. Mostly 2-6 stories. Lower density, more green, large backyards and interstices

- **Various multi-story buildings:** Multi-family housing developments mainly since the 1990s. Typically 4 stories. Semi-public green and playgrounds

- **Village cores:** Characteristic mixture of new and old structures (e.g., market place). Often local supply centers. Various building heights

- **Large housing estates:** High structures with up to 11 stories and more due to massive shortage of housing space from the 1960s–1990s. Green spaces of variable quality.

- **Detached houses (single family, semi-detached, terraced houses, e.g.):** Various detached and semi-detached house types (terraced houses to generous mansions). Low building density and private gardens.

Figure 40 Urban morphology and residential typologies in Berlin; Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2023.102890>

Berlin's spatial structure has undergone significant transformations over the past century, shaped by industrialization, war destruction, Cold War division, and post-1990 reunification. At the beginning of the 20th century, the city was characterized by a relatively compact, radial layout organized around its historic core, with limited suburban expansion. In the decades following reunification, urban development strategies combined densification within the existing fabric with expansion toward peripheral areas. According to the *Atlas of Urban Expansion*²⁰, between 2000 and 2013, growth increasingly shifted toward a more dispersed metropolitan pattern, with development occurring through infill (35%), inclusion (40%), and extension (21%) in outer districts and surrounding towns. This reflects a gradual transition from a highly compact urban model to a more complex structure integrating suburban and peri-urban areas.

At the same time, planning approaches emphasized the integration of green and open spaces into the urban fabric, contributing to a slight decrease in built-up density. This aligns with broader strategies aimed at improving environmental quality, expanding green infrastructure, and reintegrating former industrial and border zones into the city. As a result, Berlin today presents a hybrid spatial structure, combining a dense historic core with more recent suburban and peri-urban developments, interconnected through regional transport networks.

These spatial transformations are closely linked to demographic dynamics. After a period of decline and stagnation, particularly in the early 2000s, Berlin's population has experienced sustained growth since reunification, reaching approximately 3.58 million inhabitants in 2025, compared to 3.33 million in 1950. This growth has been accompanied by a gradual decentralization process, reflected in the expansion of suburban areas and the increasing presence of urbanized open spaces

Post war modernism – Bauhaus. Berlin played a key role as a centre of modernist architectural thought, particularly through its **connection to the Bauhaus movement**. The Bauhaus movement, founded in 1919 in Weimar by Walter Gropius, introduced a new approach to architecture based on the integration of art, craft, and technology. Its guiding principle was the creation of a *Gesamtkunstwerk*-a total work of art-bringing together different disciplines into a unified architectural expression. Initially rooted in craftsmanship and material understanding, the Bauhaus emphasized hands-on workshop training, where design and construction were closely linked.

During the 1920s, the Bauhaus progressively shifted toward industrial production, promoting standardization, prefabrication, and the development of prototypes for mass housing. Under the motto "art and technology – a new unity," architecture became increasingly oriented toward efficiency, functionality, and social needs. This transition was reinforced under Hannes Meyer, who emphasized rational design and industrial methods, laying the foundation for system-based construction approaches. Berlin played a key role as a cultural and professional environment for many Bauhaus figures, including Walter Gropius and Ludwig Mies van der Rohe, and served as an important testing ground for modernist ideas. Although the Bauhaus was only briefly located in Berlin between 1932 and 1933 before its closure, its influence continued to shape the city's architectural development.

Figure 41 Building at Hansaviertel, © Landesdenkmalamt Berlin, Foto: Wolfgang Bittner. <https://www.visitberlin.de/en/100-years-bauhaus-glance>

²⁰ <http://www.atlasofurbanexpansion.org/cities/view/Berlin>

After World War II, modernist principles re-emerged in projects such as the *Hansaviertel (IBA 1957)*, where international architects applied functional and socially oriented design concepts in a new urban context.

The legacy of the Bauhaus in Berlin lies less in specific materials and more in its **transformation of the building process**. Its emphasis on industrialization, modularity, and the integration of design and construction informed later developments in architecture, including contemporary timber construction.²¹²²

In Berlin–Brandenburg, cultural identity in building practices reveals a shift from natural ornamentation in timber and stone to artificial stone materials that became common between 1840–1900. As outlined in the *Wetlands and Construction* report, this period marks a transitional era in craftsmanship, where artificial cement stone (Betonstein) was developed to mimic classical elements like columns, balustrades, and decorative facades. These objects, particularly visible in palaces like Babelsberg and bourgeois villas in Pankow, held symbolic importance: they reflected an aspiration toward permanence and status, even when made from composite or impermanent materials. Although timber craftsmanship declined during this industrial era, the ornamental intent remained strong, and the new materials carried similar identity functions. The report points to Berlin’s excursion architecture of the 19th century as a symbol of middle-class recreation culture, where materials—regardless of authenticity—helped define emerging suburban aesthetics. Today, these elements are part of Berlin’s material heritage, forming a layered cultural landscape in which wood, stone, and artificial materials coexist as carriers of meaning. This also informs how contemporary timber is re-embraced, not just for function or sustainability, but as a visible sign of ecological and cultural awareness.²³

Timber has played a relatively limited role in Berlin’s historical urban development compared to rural Brandenburg. While wood was used in early construction phases, particularly in **medieval and pre-industrial settlements**, it was gradually replaced by more durable and fire-resistant materials such as **brick and stone** as the city densified. By the 19th century, Berlin’s built environment became dominated by **masonry construction, with timber primarily used for internal structural elements** such as floors and roof frameworks rather than as a visible material.

In contrast to rural timber traditions, wood in Berlin did not develop a strong vernacular architectural identity, remaining a secondary material within predominantly mineral construction systems. This tendency was further reinforced after World War II, when reconstruction in both East and West Berlin relied heavily on **concrete and prefabricated systems**, leaving little room for timber in large-scale urban housing.

Despite this limited role, timber appeared **in early modern architectural experimentation**. A notable example is the Sommerfeld House (1920–1922), designed by Walter Gropius and Adolf Meyer during the early Bauhaus period. Built using a **log construction system**, the project brought together multiple Bauhaus workshops and represented an early attempt to integrate architecture, craftsmanship, and design into a unified concept. Timber was used both structurally and decoratively, including in interior elements such as carvings, furniture, and stained glass. Although the building was destroyed during the Second World War, it remains an important reference for early modern timber architecture in Berlin.

²¹ <https://www.visitberlin.de/en/100-years-bauhaus-glance>

²² <https://www.bauhaus.de/en/discover/article/14-years-of-bauhaus/>

²³ <https://experimental-foundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/be-fellow-material-cultures-wetlands-and-construction-report-en.pdf>

Figure 42 Sommerfeld House, Berlin.
Architecture: Walter Gropius and Adolf
Meyer, 1920–1922 / Photo: Carl Rogge.

Figure 43 Walter Gropius, Adolf Meyer,
Haus Sommerfeld, Berlin (1920–
1922), Garden side, balcony soffit.
Source: bauhaus.de

Figure 44 Daniel Gut – Node of the
Packaged House System by Konrad
Wachsmann and Walter Gropius.
Source: Konrad Wachsmann
(1901/1980) – pioneer of modern wood
construction- 13. Internationales
Holzbau-Forum 2007

Figure 45 Three-dimensional node for a
demountable office partition system.
Source: Konrad Wachsmann
(1901/1980) – pioneer of modern wood
construction- 13. Internationales
Holzbau-Forum 2007

At the same time, Konrad Wachsmann played a key role in advancing timber construction toward industrialized production. His work focused on prefabrication and modular systems, particularly through the development of **panel-based construction and the “General Panel System.”** These innovations enabled the standardization of timber elements and laid the groundwork for modern timber construction by shifting from craft-based techniques to system-based, industrial approaches.

Timber construction in Berlin remained marginal throughout most of the 20th century and was largely limited to small-scale applications such as single-family houses, pavilions, and sports halls. It was only after the early 2000s that timber re-emerged as a dynamic field, supported by regulatory changes, including the 2006 amendment to the Berlin Building Code, which enabled the development of multi-storey timber buildings. This marked the beginning of a new phase, in which timber construction gradually expanded beyond niche applications.

Today, timber construction is increasingly linked to sustainability goals and climate policies, becoming part of Berlin’s broader transition toward climate-neutral urban development. Contemporary projects make growing use of engineered wood products and integrate timber into modular and hybrid systems, often in combination with steel and concrete. Timber is now applied across a wider range of building types, including residential, educational, and public buildings. Although its overall share remains relatively limited compared to conventional construction, timber architecture in Berlin has evolved rapidly in recent years. It can be understood as a field that, while historically secondary, is gaining strategic importance and reshaping the architectural landscape through innovation, environmental performance, and new construction technologies.

The *Timber Construction Atlas DE*²⁴ is a digital platform showcasing innovative timber projects in Germany, promoting wood as a sustainable alternative to conventional materials and highlighting its renewed role in contemporary, resource-efficient construction. Around **70 innovative wood projects from Berlin and Brandenburg are featured in the Atlas**, which has been available online since November 2020. It provides a comprehensive overview of contemporary timber construction

²⁴ <https://www.holzbauatlas.de/holzbauprojekte/>

in the region, including multi-story residential buildings, modular school buildings, and complex hall structures, illustrating the diverse applications of timber across different building typologies.²⁵

Figure 46 Timber projects in Germany, Brandenburg and Berlin. Source: Timber Construction Atlas DE

Figure 47 Timber hybrid construction in Berlin_Photography: Sebastian Johnke

Figure 48 Waldorf Campus Berlin_Solid wood construction_Photography: Werner Huthmacher

Figure 49 HOME B School building construction using modular timber construction, Kaufmann Building Systems. Source: www.holzbauwelt.de

Timber public buildings

Schools: To meet the high demand for schools, the State of Berlin has committed itself to constructing up to 60 new school buildings in the coming years, using standardized timber modular designs that meet modern educational, energy, and sustainability requirements. These flexible buildings can be adapted to different sites and include light-filled learning spaces and shared facilities such as cafeterias. In total, 32 of these schools were expected to be completed by 2026.²⁶ (HOME B Programme)

Daycare buildings: Launched in 2017, the MOKIB program aims to rapidly expand daycare capacity across Berlin through modular, timber-based construction. Financed by the city's SIWA infrastructure fund, four standardized building types were developed, with two implemented between 2019 and 2022. The prefabricated wooden system enables fast, cost-efficient, and low-emission construction. In total, nine facilities (types P120 and M120), each

²⁵ https://bbu.de/beitraege/holzbau-atlas-fuer-berlin-brandenburg-ist-online-ueber-70-innovative-projekte-der-region?utm_source=chatgpt.com

²⁶ <https://nkbak.de/en/homeb-berlin/>

accommodating up to 136 children, are being built across nine districts, creating 1,224 new daycare places.²⁷

Sport facilities: Berlin is rolling out standardized, modular sports halls (TSH), now focused on the TSH-K type, to enable faster, coordinated, and sustainable school infrastructure development.

Rural area

The forest cover in Brandenburg region plays a defining role in shaping the region's spatial structure. With over 37% of the territory covered by forests, including 34% deciduous trees, Brandenburg ranks among the most wooded regions in Germany. This natural abundance has historically influenced rural settlement dispersion, land use zoning, and vernacular construction techniques, especially in areas like Lusowo, where timber-framed architecture is prominent (ZRS Architekten Ingenieure, 2022).

Rural areas in Brandenburg are characterized by a range of settlement typologies shaped by a predominantly flat landscape, extensive forest cover, and a network of agricultural fields and water bodies. Settlement patterns have historically developed in relation to transport routes, land distribution systems, and agricultural organization, resulting in linear villages, compact nucleated settlements, and dispersed farmsteads.

Villages often developed along roads, canals, or former trade routes, forming elongated settlement structures with buildings aligned along a central axis. In other cases, compact village clusters emerged around a central square, green, or church, reflecting planned settlement structures. Dispersed dwellings and farm units are also present, particularly in areas with larger agricultural plots or forest clearings.

Figure 50 Rural settlement typologies in Brandenburg. Source: Google Earth

Linear street village (Straßendorf) – elongated settlement aligned along a main road

Anger village (Angerdorf) – compact settlement organized around a central green space

Clustered village (Haufendorf) – irregular, dense grouping of buildings

Dispersed farmsteads – isolated dwellings distributed across agricultural land

²⁷ <https://www.berlin.de/sen/bauen/hochbau/jugend/>

The rural built environment reflects a strong relationship between agricultural production, forestry, and settlement structure. Traditional farmsteads typically consist of a main dwelling and agricultural annexes arranged around courtyards or along plots, often following linear land division patterns.

Timber construction

In Brandenburg, traditional timber construction was historically rooted in rural practices, where wood was the primary building material used for both dwellings and defensive structures. Early construction techniques included **log construction (Blockbau)** and **squared timber systems (Schrotholzbau)**, using mainly pine, which was locally available and valued for its durability when properly treated. These techniques relied on **manual processing of timber (splitting, shaping, stacking)** and resulted in solid wooden walls and simple, robust structures adapted to local environmental conditions. Timber was locally sourced and carefully prepared, including practices that enhanced durability (e.g., stimulating resin production before felling).

Figure 51 (left) Timber rafting based on traditional models, © Otto Schinle

Figure 52 (right) Spiral removal of bark. Source: Adhesives free bark panels: An alternative application for a waste material. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280721>

The spiral removal of bark before felling stimulated resin production, enhancing the durability of the wood. After felling, the trunks were hewn into squared beams, which were stacked to construct smooth walls.

Timber framing (Fachwerk) became the dominant construction system in rural areas until the mid-19th century, reflecting a resource-efficient and locally embedded building culture, closely linked to forestry and material availability. Construction practices were based on local knowledge, craftsmanship, and the direct use of forest resources, forming part of a broader rural economy.

Timber has played a central role in Brandenburg not only as a construction material, but also as a key economic resource. As early as the 17th and 18th centuries, wood formed both the material and energy basis for industrial development and long-distance trade in the region. Its abundance supported a wide range of activities, from sawmills and glass production—often linked to the emergence of settlements—to professions such as rafting, potash production, and other resource-based occupations.

Beyond its structural use in buildings, timber was extensively employed in the production of ships, shingles, wheels, furniture, tools, and everyday objects, as well as in the manufacture of paper and musical instruments. At the same time, wood served as a primary energy source, particularly for

firing glassworks and furnaces. This multifunctional use highlights the fundamental role of forest resources in shaping both the built environment and the economic development of Brandenburg.

In rural Brandenburg, **Fachwerk buildings** were typically organized as part of **agricultural farmsteads, combining residential, storage, and productive functions** within cohesive spatial ensembles. The construction system relied on a visible wooden structural frame, with non-loadbearing infill made of clay, brick, or other locally available materials. This approach allowed for a reduction in timber use compared to solid log construction, while maintaining structural stability and adaptability. Buildings were generally low-rise, with simple rectangular volumes, pitched roofs, and flexible internal layouts that could be adjusted over time according to changing needs.

The Fachwerk system also enabled incremental transformation, as infill panels could be replaced, repaired, or upgraded without altering the structural frame. As a result, many buildings evolved over time through extensions, material substitutions, or façade modifications, reflecting changing socio-economic conditions and construction practices. Today, many of these buildings have been adapted or plastered, but they continue to reflect the region's vernacular building culture and its close relationship with local resources and rural life.

Figure 53 Sorbian villages in northern Upper Lusatia were also characterised by timber construction. Source: <https://umgebendehaus.hszg.de/service/fotogalerie>

Figure 54 Two common fachwerk systems. Source: <https://www.sddu.com.ua/en/technologies/fachwerk>

Timber-framed barns (*Fachwerkscheunen*) in Brandenburg and Berlin (17th–19th centuries) are robust agricultural buildings designed for storage and processing of crops. Their architecture is defined by a timber framework (mainly pine and occasionally oak or elm for key elements), with infill of clay, boards, or brick, and steeply pitched roofs to maximize storage and protect against weather. Interiors feature a central threshing floor and large bays for grain and hay, accessed by oversized double doors. Unlike timber-framed houses, which prioritize comfort and aesthetics, barns focus on utility, durability, and open space. Regional variations exist in construction details and materials, but the core design remains consistent, reflecting the practical needs of rural communities and the evolution of agricultural practices.²⁸

The **industrialization period marked a major shift in construction practices**. The introduction of new materials such as steel and concrete, together with improved transport systems, reduced

²⁸ Schmidt, K.W., [year]. *The development of barn architecture in Brandenburg and Berlin: Transversely accessed half-timbered barns after the Thirty Years' War until the mid-19th century*. Berlin: Technische Universität Berlin.

dependence on local resources and led to a significant decline in timber construction. By the late 19th century, wood had largely been replaced in mainstream construction, and its use became increasingly marginal.

In the early 20th century, timber construction experienced a partial revival through technological innovation and prefabrication. Architects such as Konrad Wachsmann developed more efficient timber systems, including panel-based and skeletal structures, enabling faster construction and greater standardization. Projects like Einstein's summer house in Caputh exemplify this transition toward industrialized timber construction.

Figure 55 (left) House Vilmar in Kleinmachnow. Werner Schenk | Müller-Stüler und Höll Architekten, © Florian Höll. "Planning and Building with Wood in Brandenburg" ZRS Architekten Ingenieure

Figure 56 (right) Einstein's summer house in Caputh. Konrad Wachsmann | Einstein Forum, © Hans Bach. Source: "Planning and Building with Wood in Brandenburg" ZRS Architekten Ingenieure

However, after World War II, construction practices in Brandenburg shifted decisively toward **mineral-based materials, and timber played only a secondary role**, particularly in large-scale housing and urban development.

In recent decades, timber has re-emerged as a key material in sustainable construction, supported by advances in engineered wood products and growing environmental concerns. Wood is now recognized for its capacity to reduce CO₂ emissions, lower the use of non-renewable resources, and support circular building approaches. The use of timber has been increasing, particularly in **new buildings, including residential, commercial, and public structures**.

Brandenburg's forests provide a diverse range of timber species, with pine being the most characteristic, alongside oak, beech, spruce, and larch. Each species has specific physical and mechanical properties, influencing its application in construction, from structural elements to interior finishes.

The Berlin–Brandenburg region demonstrates a **strong spatial relationship between woodland cover and settlement structure**. With forests accounting for more than a third of Brandenburg's land area, dispersed rural villages historically developed along forest edges, where timber could be easily sourced (Experimental Foundation, 2024). This ecological proximity shaped vernacular half-timbered building traditions, linking settlement form directly to material availability. The maps of land use and woodland distribution emphasize the continuing relevance of woodland-settlement dynamics, not only as a spatial reality but as a foundation for material-based (urban) design strategies.

Despite these advantages, timber construction still faces perception barriers, often associated with low durability or temporary structures, rooted in historical experiences with simple or emergency buildings. However, this image is gradually changing, as timber architecture is increasingly associated with quality, sustainability, and positive user perception. Studies indicate that wooden buildings can enhance the reputation of companies and institutions, contributing to a more favorable public image.²⁹

Recent material innovation reflected in Brandenburg is centered around biobased materials that are circular and locally sourced. A notable development is the use of Typha (cattail) from rewetted peatlands as a sustainable insulation material. The Typha panels that are biodegradable and magnesite-bound offer comparable thermal performance to conventional options while reducing dependency on water-intensive timber species. Such an approach is in line with the broader Brandenburg policies that prioritize low-impact construction using renewable biomass (Experimental Foundation, 2024).

Figure 57 Apartment building in Potsdam. Solid, glue-free wooden construction. Source: Jan Bitter, Berlin. baunetzwissen.de

Figure 58 Waldorf School Kleinmachnow (2016)

Figure 59 Green bridge Luckenwalde, Schwesig in Brandenburg. Photography: René Legrand <https://www.holzbauatlas.de>

However, in recent decades, timber has resurged both as a technologically advanced material and a symbol of ecological transition. Recent architectural projects across Brandenburg illustrate this trend. Examples include the timber-framed administration building in Paulinenaue (2021), the arched glued-laminated timber (glulam) bridge in Luckenwalde, the canteen of the Eberswalde University of Applied Sciences (2013), and multi-storey residential buildings like the *Holzhaus am Waldpark* in Kleinmachnow. These structures employ modern timber technologies such as CNC milling, CLT (cross-laminated timber), and glulam beams—often combined with steel or concrete to meet structural needs.³⁰

²⁹ “Planning and Building with Wood in Brandenburg” ZRS Architekten Ingenieure, Ministry of Infrastructure and Regional Planning of the State of Brandenburg (MIL) and in cooperation with the Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection, the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Energy and the Brandenburg Economic Development Corporation. <https://www.zrs.berlin/en/article/9716/>

³⁰ <https://www.zrs.berlin/en/article/9716/>

At the same time, there is a renewed appreciation for historic wooden constructions, such as the Slavic Castle in Raddusch, reconstructed as part of a cultural heritage initiative to protect and preserve ancient carpentry techniques and spatial configurations.³¹

Industrial production reinforces this transition to structural timber: firms such as the CLASSEN Group in Baruth operate integrated cycles that transform raw timber into laminate, glulam, and fiberboard, utilizing by-products for biomass energy (CLASSEN Group, n.d.). These localized value chains bridge rural resource extraction with urban innovation, underlining Brandenburg's role as a competence hub for timber processing and sustainable construction (ZRS Architekten Ingenieure, 2022).

However, alongside this shift toward industrialization and innovation, there are examples on the preservation and reinterpretation of traditional timber heritage. The restoration of a 250-year-old timber-frame (Fachwerk) farmhouse in Lunow illustrates how vernacular architecture can be adapted to contemporary standards without losing its identity. Built with locally sourced wood and clay, the structure reflects the long-standing vernacular tradition of timber construction in Brandenburg, shaped by the availability of surrounding forest resources. The restoration used natural materials and integrated renewable energy solutions, such as solar panels, demonstrating how heritage values can be preserved while meeting modern energy standards. Details such as exposed timber beams and historic wall layers illustrate the blend of traditional craftsmanship with contemporary sustainability practices.³²

Figure 60 Modernisation and simultaneous historical restoration of a 250-year-old farmhouse. Lunow-Stolzenhagen, Brandenburg, Germany. Source: kfw.de

The transition marks a clear cultural and material shift: from viewing wood as a rural relic to embracing it as a modern, flexible and sustainable material. In Berlin-Brandenburg, timber now stands at the intersection of tradition and innovation, sustainability and design-positioned not only as a construction material but as a medium of regional identity and ecological action.

³¹ <https://safarway.com/en/property/slavic-castle-raddusch>

³² <https://www.kfw.de/stories/society/housing/kfw-award-2019-construction-lunow/>

3.3. Siena, Italy

Siena (53,062 inhabitants in 2021³³) is a historic city in central Italy, located in the Tuscany region. It is widely recognized for its well-preserved medieval urban fabric and strong cultural identity, shaped by its role as a major economic and political center during the Middle Ages.

According to the Istituto Nazionale di Statistica Italia, Siena's population declined from the 1980s to the early 2000s and has since stabilized with only slight recent growth.³⁴ Administratively, Siena functions at multiple levels within the Italian territorial system. It is a *comune* (municipality) - the basic unit of local governance - and also serves as the capital of the Province of Siena, which encompasses a wider predominantly rural territory. The province itself is part of the Tuscany region, one of Italy's main administrative and planning levels.

Figure 61 Urban–Rural Typology of Southern Italy (NUTS 3); Source: Eurostat, 2024

Figure 62 Province of Siena in Tuscany region (bottom left). Source: wikipedia

Figure 63 Siena contrade (bottom right). Source: David Lown: www.picturesfromitaly.com

³³ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/italy/toscana/siena/052032_siena/

³⁴ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/italy/toscana/siena/052032_siena/

The NUTS level 3 classification from Eurostat (2024) provides a territorial overview of urban–rural dynamics across Italy. Within this framework, the Province of Siena (IT119) is categorized as a **predominantly rural region**, highlighting the strong presence of agricultural and low-density landscapes. This classification reflects the spatial structure of the area, where the historic urban center of Siena is embedded within a predominantly rural and agricultural territory. It supports the understanding of Tuscany as a cohesive urban–rural system, characterized by strong functional relationships between city and countryside.

This configuration is essential for interpreting the region’s cultural continuity and land-use patterns, where compact historic settlements coexist with and are supported by actively cultivated landscapes.

Figure 64 Aerial Perspective of Siena.
Source: unsplash

Figure 65 Aerial Perspective Siena Map.
Source: GoogleEarth

Urban area

Siena is a historic city that combines features of the pre-industrial urban environment with elements typical of small villages in the surrounding territory. Through this combination, the city becomes a relevant example for understanding the complex relationship between buildings and the land on which they are built.

Unlike large metropolitan capitals such as Berlin, Siena has maintained a compact urban structure centered around its historic core, the Historic Centre of Siena. The city is characterized by a dense network of narrow streets, civic spaces, and distinctive districts (*contrade*), reflecting a strong relationship between urban form, social organization, and local traditions.

Figure 66 Piazza Del Campo – Historic core (medieval fabric) and neighborhood units.
Source: Unsplash

Figure 67 Tourism and Leisure-oriented areas. Source: Google Earth

The spatial morphology of Siena is shaped by its medieval origins, resulting in a **compact, concentric** urban form characterized by irregular street networks and ‘expressive’ public spaces. The compactness of the medieval core supports walkability and reinforces the integration of civic, religious, and residential functions within a dense urban fabric. The ‘Piazza del Campo’, represents one of the most iconic urban squares in Europe, emerging from the convergence of key streets and the adaptation to topography. The surrounding built fabric demonstrates Siena’s highly structured and unified appearance, with institutional and private buildings grouped in a way that accentuates visual rhythm and spatial coherence (Moccia & Secondo, 2017). The skyline is punctuated by towers and churches, reflecting a clear distinction between public and private buildings based on scale and architectural articulation. These features highlight Siena’s strong identity rooted in its medieval civic organisation and its emphasis on spatial symbolism and order.

Figure 68 Productive and infrastructural areas. Source: Google Earth
Figure 69 Individual housing outside the historic wall. Source: Google Earth

- **Historic core (medieval fabric)**
Compact and highly dense urban fabric, characterized by irregular street patterns, narrow alleys, and buildings aligned along continuous street fronts. The morphology reflects adaptation to topography and historic defensive constraints, with strong spatial enclosure and a mix of residential, civic, and commercial functions.
- **Historic neighborhood units (fine-grained fabric)**
Subdivisions of the historic core characterized by dense building patterns, narrow interconnected streets, and small public spaces such as small squares and courtyards. These areas follow the irregular medieval structure and maintain continuity of built frontages and compact parceling.
- **Late 20th-century residential areas**
Planned expansions outside the historic walls, with more regular street layouts, lower density compared to the historic core, and a mix of apartment buildings and individual housing. These areas are designed to accommodate modern mobility patterns and service provision.
- **Tourism and leisure-oriented areas**
Urban spaces shaped or adapted to accommodate tourism flows and leisure activities, including major public squares, cultural facilities, green spaces, and panoramic viewpoints. These areas are often embedded within or adjacent to the historic core and are characterized by high pedestrian accessibility and strong connections to heritage assets.
- **Productive and commercial areas**
Designated zones located mainly at the urban periphery, characterized by larger building footprints, functional layouts, and strong dependence on road infrastructure. These areas accommodate light industrial activities, logistics, and commercial functions, forming spatially distinct enclaves compared to the historic fabric.

Peri-urban / rural interface

Transitional zones where urban development meets agricultural land, characterized by dispersed settlements, villas, agritourism facilities, and farmsteads integrated into productive landscapes such as vineyards and olive groves.

Figure 70 Historical Maps of Siena;
Source_ http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9413-1_13

Figure 71 Core Zone, the officially designated UNESCO World Heritage area. Source: unesco.org

Figure 72 (bottom right) Map showing the UNESCO Core Zone (red line) alongside the Buffer Zone, which serves as a protective perimeter; Source: unesco.org

The city's architectural landscape is primarily defined by its distinctive Gothic character, developed between the 12th and 15th centuries, with later interventions incorporating Renaissance elements while maintaining strong continuity with the established Gothic language.

The historical maps of Siena illustrate the city's compact medieval core embedded within a terrain of steep valleys and ridges, reflecting the topographic constraints that shaped its growth. The earlier map (1869) shows a dense urban nucleus concentrated around the central squares and main roads, with minimal extension into the surrounding hills. By contrast, the later representation highlights a more developed urban fabric, with expanded street networks, additional built-up areas, and infrastructural elements such as the San Domenico–Fortezza viaduct.

When compared with a more contemporary map of Siena, the persistence of the historical core is evident, yet gradual expansion and adaptation to modern mobility and land use needs have reshaped certain edges of the city. Together, these maps reveal a slow but steady urban expansion influenced by both historical preservation priorities and the constraints of the surrounding landscape.

This map identifies only the Core Zone, the officially designated UNESCO World Heritage area. The Core Zone includes the historic urban fabric, architectural landmarks, and cultural spaces that embody Siena's heritage significance. Strict preservation regulations apply within this area to maintain its authenticity and integrity.

The Buffer Zone surrounds the core zone to protect it from potential external threats such as modern construction, visual intrusion, or infrastructure development. While the buffer zone allows more flexible land use than the core zone, it is still subject to coordinated heritage management measures to avoid negative impacts on the protected site.

Palazzi (civic & aristocratic buildings) - Large, representative buildings characterized by regular façades, symmetrical compositions, and internal courtyards. Constructed using high-quality materials and refined stonework, these buildings historically accommodated administrative, political, and elite residential functions, contributing to the city's monumental character.

Religious buildings (churches and cathedrals) - Churches, monasteries, and associated structures that are architecturally and spatially prominent. Often positioned on elevated points or within key urban spaces, they feature distinctive volumes, towers, and ornamentation, playing a central role in shaping the skyline and identity of Siena.

Attached historic buildings (medieval fabric) - Narrow, vertically developed buildings forming continuous street frontages within the historic core. These structures are typically organized along irregular street networks, with mixed-use ground floors and residential upper levels. Their compact form reflects adaptation to limited space and topography.

Apartment buildings (20th century) - Multi-family residential buildings located primarily outside the historic core, characterized by simplified architectural language and modern construction techniques. These buildings typically accommodate higher densities and are organized within planned residential developments.

Detached and semi-detached housing - Individual or paired residential buildings, generally located in peripheral areas. These structures are characterized by lower density, the presence of private gardens, and layouts adapted to the hilly terrain, often representing a transition between urban and rural environments.

Modernist buildings (20th-century insertions) - Buildings developed mainly during the mid-late 20th century, characterized by simplified geometric forms, flat or low pitched roofs, and the use of modern materials such as reinforced concrete, glass, and plaster - typically located outside the historic core or at its edges.

Figure 73 Catedrala din Siena, Palazzo Pubblico and Torre del Mangia, Attached historic buildings (medieval fabric), Traditional residential buildings detaches and semi-detached. Multiple sources

Figure 74 Modernist buildings. Source: googlemaps

Figure 75 Siena – examples of composite structures interacting and articulated according to the slope configuration: Palazzo del Governo and a model of terraced houses in the Contrada del Bruco.

Figure 76 Arches and overpasses connecting buildings across narrow streets in Siena (left), compared with a similar configuration in Arquata del Tronto (right). Source: <https://doi.org/10.36153/baa8.07>

A defining characteristic of traditional construction in Siena is the **structural integration of adjacent buildings**, which function not as independent units but as interconnected systems. This approach, evident in the widespread use of attached and terraced building typologies, allows for mutual support between structures and enhances overall stability, particularly in response to seismic forces. The continuity of masonry walls, floors, and roof systems enables interaction between neighbouring buildings, creating a collective structural behaviour at the scale of the urban fabric. This is further reinforced by the city's hilly topography, where buildings adapt to slope conditions and often rely on one another for support, forming configurations that improve resistance to external stresses. Premodern construction techniques—including the use of tie rods, buttresses, arches, and timber elements embedded within masonry—contribute to this integrated system. Together, these solutions reflect a body of empirical knowledge developed over centuries, where construction practices evolved through continuous adaptation, resulting in a resilient and cohesive built environment.³⁵

³⁵ Cangi, G. (n.d.). *Premodern building criteria and anti-seismic techniques in the city of Siena. Library of Architectural Archaeology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.36153/baa8.07>

Figure 77 Wood and stone reinforcements in premodern Siena architecture: examples of corner connections, tie rods, and anti-seismic construction techniques; Source: <https://doi.org/10.36153/baa8.07>

The structural reinforcement techniques used to play a crucial role in addressing the **weaknesses of masonry buildings, especially in a seismic context**. Wood and stone were often combined to strengthen vulnerable areas such as corner connections and floor levels. Wooden beams, arranged as tie rods, were integrated into the walls to counteract lateral forces, limit deformation, and reduce the risk of collapse during seismic events.

Stone elements were strategically placed to provide compression resistance at key junctions, enhancing overall structural stability. This combination of materials reflects the city's adaptation to local geological and seismic conditions, based on empirical knowledge rather than formal engineering theory. Tie rods played a key role in stabilizing masonry, preventing wall tilting and improving resistance to dynamic stresses, while remaining discreetly integrated into the urban fabric. In addition to internal reinforcement systems, external elements such as arches, vaults, and overpasses connecting buildings across narrow streets contributed to structural continuity. These transversal elements helped distribute loads between adjacent structures and improved seismic performance.

Together, these techniques illustrate a locally adapted construction logic, shaped by long-standing building traditions and practical experience.³⁶

Located in the center of Tuscany, Siena, retains a construction culture deeply rooted in **stone and brick masonry**, shaped over centuries by strong heritage conservation frameworks. Within the UNESCO-designated historic core, the housing typologies are typically dense, multi-story masonry structures aligned to an irregular medieval street grid (Cangi, n.d.).

Travertine, historically used since the Etruscan period, continues to appear in both civic and residential architecture, particularly in ornamental features, reflecting the integration of local geology into building traditions (Rescic et al., 2024).

In the city of Siena, architecture reflects a remarkably well-preserved medieval stylistic unity, recognized as part of the UNESCO World Heritage. From the 13th century onwards, and more consistently from the 15th century, travertine sourced from the Rapolano area was widely used alongside Triassic cavernous limestone and brick.

³⁶ Cangi, G. (n.d.). *Premodern building criteria and anti-seismic techniques in the city of Siena*. *Library of Architectural Archaeology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.36153/baa8.07>

Travertine served primarily as façade cladding and architectural decoration, applied to window frames, cornices, columns, sills, and thresholds. It is found in significant buildings such as the Palazzo delle Papesse, in the façades of churches like Santa Maria di Provenzano, San Giorgio, and San Martino, and in isolated elements like the cornice of the Palazzo Pubblico tower.

Beyond its historical use, Siena also offers contemporary examples where travertine is integrated into modern urban design. A notable case is the Monte dei Paschi bank business centre, built between 1983 and 1993, where Rapolano travertine cladding is combined with brick to form an architectural language that respects the historic fabric. This continued use of travertine in both religious and civic architecture, as well as in modern interventions, highlights the material's role as a marker of local identity and a symbolic connector between past and present in Siena's urban landscape.³⁷

Figure 78 Facade of Santa Maria in Provenzano, Siena. Source: wikipedia

Figure 79 The travertine cladding of the façade of Santa Maria di Provenzano (Siena, XVIIth century) - (credit Fabio Fratini). Source: Historical Use of Travertine in the Tuscan Architecture (Italy) - pdf

Most of Siena's historic buildings are made from a specific type of brick, dark red in color, which serves as the most unifying element of the city's architecture.

While the exterior facades mostly feature brick and stone, timber remains integral within the internal structural system - serving in roof trusses, floors, windows, and door frames, providing durability and endurance.

Historically, wood in Siena's construction served purposes that went beyond structural necessity. Archaeological and architectural evidence points to its use in religious artifacts, decorative panels, and foundation piles, reflecting its practical and symbolic value within the city's artistic and cultural framework (Cangi, n.d.). In addition to the artisanal traditions - notably ceramic production and metalworking - have further enhanced the region's material culture, linking architectural expression to environmental resources and local craftsmanship (Gliozzo et al., 2011).

Figure 80 Palazzo Sansedoni. Source: <https://architectureofcities.com/siena>

³⁷ Fratini, F., Rescic, S., Arrighetti, A., Cantisani, E., & Pecchioni, E. (2022). *Pietra Alberese: From traditional building material of the Tuscan countryside to the present use (Tuscany, Italy)*. *Geoheritage*, 14, 51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12371-022-00681-0>

Figure 81 Wooden Inlays of the Choir by Fra Giovanni Da Verona. Source: www.sienatickets.com

Figure 82 Traditional wooden door integrated into a stone façade in Siena. Source: [unsplash](https://unsplash.com)

Figure 83 Siena Palazzo Pubblico Loggia woodwork. Source: [Wikimedia.org](https://www.wikimedia.org)

Figure 84 Wooden beam ceiling. Medieval and modern design integration. Medieval Palace project by CMT architetti Source: homeadore.com

Cultural identity plays a central role in shaping architectural expression in Siena, where design practices reflect a strong continuity of artistic, material, and spatial traditions.

Craftsmanship is a defining component of this identity, particularly in masonry work, façade detailing, and the integration of structural and decorative elements. Traditional crafts—such as woodwork, metalwork, and ceramics—have historically supported building practices, contributing to both the functionality and the refinement of architectural expression. These practices reflect a close relationship between available resources, local skills, and construction techniques.

Figure 85 Siena Palio. Source: <https://www.corbula.it/storie-miti-e-leggende/palio-di-siena/>

Siena's cultural identity is deeply intertwined with its medieval urban form, the 'contrade system' (seventeen historic neighbourhoods, each with its own heraldry, colours, and social organisation), and the public rituals that animate the civic space. The 'Palio di Siena', a biannual horse race held in Piazza del Campo, remains a defining event that transforms the historic centre into a stage for collective identity, reinforcing bonds between residents and their respective contrade (Ascheri & Franco, 2019; UNESCO, n.d.).

Rural area

Rural areas in Tuscany, particularly in the province of Siena, are characterized by a variety of settlement typologies shaped by a predominantly hilly landscape, defined by rolling hills, ridgelines, and agricultural valleys. Settlement patterns have historically developed in close relation to topography, land use, and agricultural practices, resulting in a mix of hilltop villages, dispersed farmsteads, and linear settlements along local roads.

Figure 86 Rural landscape_San Gimignano. Source: Unsplash

Villages are often located on elevated positions for defensive and climatic reasons, forming compact clusters with dense building arrangements and clear spatial boundaries. In contrast, the surrounding countryside is characterized by dispersed rural settlements, including isolated farmhouses and small agricultural complexes integrated into productive landscapes of vineyards, olive groves, and fields.

Figure 87 Rural settlement patterns Source: Google Earth

- Hilltop compact settlements** – dense village clusters located on ridgelines (e.g Monteriggioni)
- Dispersed farmsteads** – isolated rural buildings distributed across agricultural land (e.g between Pienza and San Quirico d'Orcia)
- Clustered rural hamlets** (“Borghi”) – small groups of buildings forming semi-compact settlements
- Linear settlements along local roads** – development following infrastructure and valley routes (e.g Isola d'Arbia)

Agricultural estate complexes – larger farm units (e.g. podere) with multiple buildings (e.g Podere Belvedere)

The rural built environment reflects a strong integration between natural and productive landscapes, where settlements are closely linked to agricultural use and land management. Traditional rural units typically consist of a main dwelling accompanied by agricultural annexes, organized according to functional needs and terrain conditions. This spatial organization often combines compact settlement cores with dispersed elements, creating a gradual transition between built areas and cultivated land.

The construction traditions of Tuscany are closely tied to the **region’s natural context**, which provides a wide range of stone materials, including **sandstone, limestone, travertine, marl, and alberese**. This diversity reflects the complex geological composition of the region and explains the variety of materials available across different areas, contributing to distinct local color palettes and architectural expressions in cities such as Siena, San Gimignano, Montepulciano, and Pienza.

At the regional level, specific materials are associated with particular territories—for example, travertine deposits in Rapolano and thermal areas such as Saturnia, or clay-rich zones in Val d’Elsa and Val di Chiana, which supported brick production. These localized resources have historically shaped construction practices and material choices across Tuscany.

In the Siena area, this diversity of resources enabled the widespread use of locally available materials, particularly in masonry and façade construction. Travertine, sourced from nearby quarries such as Rapolano, was used for architectural detailing, while the availability of clay supported the extensive use of brick.³⁸

Figure 88 Most important deposits of travertine and calcareous tufa in Tuscany. Source: Historical Use of Travertine in the Tuscan Architecture (Italy), <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7010017>

Figure 89 Localities mentioned in the text where travertine has been extensively used. Source: Historical Use of Travertine in the Tuscan Architecture (Italy), <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7010017>

³⁸ Historical Use of Travertine in the Tuscan Architecture (Italy). <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7010017>

Figure 90 Pietra Alberese and Traditional Tuscan rural house constructed with Pietra Alberese; Source: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12371-022-00681-0>

In the countryside between Siena and Florence, as well as in notable Tuscan towns such as Prato and Pistoia, the local limestone known as *Pietra Alberese* has been extensively employed in both vernacular and monumental architecture. This grey marly limestone, prized for its resistance to decay and was historically the only limestone quarried locally, making it a principal construction resource in the region.

Its durability and workable nature contributed to its widespread application in masonry, facades, and lime production. Over the centuries, *Pietra Alberese* has shaped the architectural identity of villages and towns, harmonising with local typologies and colour palettes. While historically sourced primarily from nearby outcrops due to limited transport options, the 20th century saw its increased use in restoration works and integration into new buildings, reinforcing its enduring presence in the Tuscan built environment.

Craftsmanship

Craft traditions in Tuscany are closely linked to the availability of local resources and have developed as place-specific practices across the region. Different territories have specialized in particular materials and techniques, such as ceramics, textiles, glassmaking, terracotta, stone carving, and woodcraft, reflecting a strong relationship between natural resources and production. These traditions, often rooted in medieval or earlier periods, continue to shape local economies and cultural identity. The persistence of these crafts highlights the role of artisanal knowledge in transforming raw materials into both functional and symbolic objects, reinforcing the connection between landscape, material use, and regional identity.³⁹

The Tuscan tradition of wood furniture, rooted in Renaissance artistry and rural craftsmanship, is undergoing a contemporary transformation. Through restoration, reuse, and sustainable forestry, Tuscany is embracing a circular approach to wood use while preserving the cultural identity embedded in its materials and designs.

Many Tuscan homes and agriturismi now combine: rustic materials (old wood, wrought iron) with modern design (minimalist lines, modular furniture)

Tuscany has large areas of chestnut forests, especially in the Casentino and Mugello regions. Sustainable management programs promote local wood use, reducing transport emissions and supporting biodiversity. Wood from these forests is used both for structural purposes and interiors (floors, furniture, ceilings).

³⁹ <https://www.visittuscany.com/en/ideas/the-best-artisan-production-in-tuscany/>

Woodcraft traditions in Tuscany are closely linked to the region's agricultural landscape, particularly the widespread presence of olive groves. Olive wood, valued for its durability, fine grain, and distinctive appearance, has long been used for the production of tools, furniture, and decorative objects. Its use dates back to early historical periods and reflects the reliance on locally available resources. Unlike conventional timber extraction, olive wood is typically obtained through the pruning of mature trees, illustrating a resource-efficient approach and a long-standing relationship between land management and material use. These practices highlight the role of craftsmanship in transforming local materials into functional and cultural artefacts, reinforcing the connection between landscape, production, and regional identity.⁴⁰

Contemporary perspective

Contemporary developments in Tuscany also explore **timber as a sustainable building solution**. A notable example is the **temporary social housing project** in Florence's Novoli district, consisting of prefabricated modular timber units designed for rapid assembly and energy efficiency (Bellini & Macchi, 2015).

Figure 91 Temporary social housing in timber – Florence, Novoli; Source: Source: #06 Social Housing in Italia - U3 i Quaderni - pdf

This juxtaposition of historical stone traditions with modern timber innovation highlights the **region's adaptability**: traditional stonework anchors identity and cultural continuity, while timber introduces flexibility and ecological responsiveness in present-day construction. This project in the Novoli district of Florence exemplifies innovation in temporary social housing, using prefabricated timber modules. The structure is fully demountable, reversible, and recyclable, while integrating photovoltaic systems that cover up to 60% of its energy demand. With its rapid construction process and sustainable materials, the project demonstrates how timber can address urgent housing needs while ensuring high energy efficiency.⁴¹

Figure 92 Ciclostile Architettura in Tuscany. Source: designboom.com

⁴⁰ <https://www.arpiwoodworking.com/blog/the-history-of-olive-wood-craftsmanship-in-tuscany>

⁴¹ chrome-extension://efaidnbnmnibpcjpcglclefindmkaj/https://urbanisticatre.uniroma3.it/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/U3_quaderni_06_cattani_ferrante.pdf

The Ciclostile Architettura project in Tuscany focuses on the use of materials and integration with the historical and environmental context. By reinterpreting tradition, a new aesthetic language was created, linked to tradition, while valuing local techniques and materials.

The renovation of a 600 sq.m. farmhouse across three levels involved the use of recycled materials such as terracotta and wood to maintain a connection with tradition, but with a contemporary approach. The terracotta floors were replaced with recycled tiles, and in the sleeping areas, a wood design was used to recreate a traditional pattern.

Steel played a significant role, used both structurally and aesthetically, through elements like the corten steel staircase and the double-sided fireplace, highlighting interventions on the existing building while preserving the marks of time.⁴²

Figure 93 Casa Citeria in Tuscany. Source: designboom.com

Casa Citeria is a renovated private residence located in Tuscany. Originally part of a historic rural building later subdivided into multiple units, the house had undergone several transformations during the 20th century, which replaced many traditional architectural elements with modern, often incongruous solutions. These changes altered both the spatial organization and the building's relationship to its historical context.

The renovation aimed to restore the building's original character, both in terms of spatial layout and construction quality, while reinterpreting it for contemporary living. Traditional local materials such as terracotta, lime, chestnut wood, and stone were used to create a modern yet contextually rooted architectural language. At the same time, the project integrated a comprehensive set of energy efficiency upgrades, employing natural, historically appropriate materials to align with current sustainability standards.⁴³

⁴² <https://www.designboom.com/architecture/ciclostile-farmhouse-italy-06-11-201>

⁴³ <https://www.designboom.com/architecture/ciclostile-farmhouse-italy-06-11-2018/>

4. TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey

4.1. Baia Mare, Romania

Based on the 21 responses collected, the results for Baia Mare provide a clear and consistent picture of the local construction landscape and the role of wood across urban and rural contexts. The stakeholder profile is predominantly composed of participants from the Construction and Design group (16 respondents) and complemented by the perspectives provided by the Heritage and Craftsmanship group (5 respondents).

BAIA MARE - MARAMUREȘ		
	Urban Areas	Rural Areas
Key challenges affecting the use of wood in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong dominance of conventional materials such as concrete and brick, limiting the uptake of timber solutions; • Regulatory constraints, especially fire safety and approval processes, create uncertainty and discourage adoption; • Limited technical capacity and shortage of skilled workforce for timber construction; • Low level of prefabrication and industrialization, reducing competitiveness of timber systems; • Weak demand driven by low investor confidence in wood as a structural material; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial constraints and cost-driven decisions limit the adoption of higher-quality or innovative timber solutions; • Loss of traditional knowledge and lack of skilled craftsmen reduce the effective use of wood; • Perception of wood as less durable and requiring higher maintenance affects material choices; • Increasing influence of urban construction models leads to replacement of traditional wood-based practices; • Limited access to training, innovation, and institutional support;
Key opportunities for expanding the use of wood in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High potential in renovation and heritage-related projects, where wood is already better integrated; • Strong acceptance of wood in non-structural applications, creating entry points for wider use; • Growing pressure for energy efficiency and NZEB compliance supports timber solutions; • Potential for prefabricated timber systems to improve efficiency and scalability; • Opportunity to integrate and reinterpret traditional techniques in contemporary architecture; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong availability of local timber resources and existing use of wood as a structural material; • Potential to revive and upgrade traditional techniques through skills development; • Opportunities linked to tourism, cultural projects, and heritage-based development • Integration of traditional knowledge into sustainable and locally adapted construction practices;

Figure 94 Key challenges and opportunities identified based on stakeholders qualitative answers in Baia Mare

General information

The responses to Question 1 confirm that all 21 participants are active in Baia Mare and its surrounding area, ensuring a locally grounded and context-relevant dataset. Additionally, **76.2%** of respondents belong to the **“Construction and design - architects, engineers, builders, urban planners, professional associations”** group, while **23.8%** are part of the **“Heritage and craftsmanship - craftsmen, artisans, heritage experts, cultural institutions, craft schools”** group.

Figure 95 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

The distribution of responses indicates a heterogeneous professional structure across the wood value chain. **Engineering (28.6%) and architecture (14.3%)** represent the dominant fields, while **construction, forestry, and renovation (each 9.5%)** contribute to a broader technical base. The presence of additional sectors, including environmental protection, culture, and planning, reflects a multi-sectoral stakeholder composition.

Figure 96 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 5

Figure 97 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 7

For Question 5, the results indicate a low level of institutionalized collaboration within the wood value chain, with 81% of respondents not engaged in any cluster or association. As reflected in Question 6, collaborations are limited to a small set of actors (e.g., SC RUSTIC SRL, AIM, Direcția Silvică MM, and traditional wood craftsmen), suggesting a fragmented network structure. Question 7 indicates that most projects are located in rural or mixed urban-rural contexts (48%), compared to a smaller share in exclusively urban areas (33%) and a marginal presence in forest contexts (5%). This distribution reflects the territorial scope of stakeholder activity beyond the urban core.

Urban Areas
CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN
Local construction practices

Figure 98 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 1

Figure 99 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 2

Question 1 indicates that new construction is the most frequent project type in the local urban area (38%), followed by renovation (31%). This distribution reflects the coexistence of expansion processes and interventions on the existing building stock, defining the current urban development pattern.

Question 2 shows that construction in the local urban area is primarily carried out through on-site methods (63%), while prefabricated solutions are used only to a limited extent (19%) and are not widely adopted. This pattern indicates a strong dependence on conventional construction practices, with low uptake of industrialized building approaches.

Figure 100 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 3

Figure 101 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a diverse material use in urban new construction. Structural use is led by **concrete (29%)** and **brick (26%)**, followed by **wood (23%)**, while **stone (6%)** and **steel (11%)** have lower shares. For exterior applications, **brick (25%)** and **wood (19%)** are most prevalent, followed by **stone (14%)** and **concrete (14%)**, with other materials remaining limited.

Figure 102 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a moderate perception of sustainability in current urban construction practices, with most responses concentrated at a medium level and a significant share reflecting more positive evaluations.

Qualitative responses (Question 6) highlight several structural constraints affecting sustainability. A key issue is the gap between principles and implementation, as many investors do not fully understand or apply sustainability policies in practice. This is reinforced by development patterns prioritizing efficiency over sustainability, with urban growth driven more by volume and speed of execution than by the use of durable materials or low-impact solutions. Another consistent finding is the continued dominance of conventional materials, including concrete and brick, alongside a limited integration of renewable alternatives. Within this context, wood is repeatedly identified as an underutilized resource, with potential for broader application in both structural elements and exterior uses. At the same time, some responses acknowledge that outcomes depend on the type of investment, while references to traditional construction knowledge suggest that local techniques could support more sustainable approaches if better integrated into contemporary projects.

Overall, the results indicate a partial and uneven integration of sustainability, shaped by material choices, development practices, and implementation gaps, while also pointing to clear opportunities related to renewable materials and local construction traditions.

Figure 103 Figure 104 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 7

Figure 104 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 8

- “Most investors do not understand or apply sustainability policies in construction.”
- “Urban growth is driven by volume and speed of execution rather than sustainable materials or low-impact solutions.”
- “Wood has potential for broader application, both in structural elements and exterior applications.”

Questions 7 and 8 indicate a diverse material profile in urban renovation. Structural use is dominated by brick (26%) and wood (23%), followed by concrete (21%) and stone (15%), while steel (8%) has a lower share. For exterior applications, brick (30%) and wood (30%) are most prevalent, followed by stone (19%), while glass (5%) and metal (8%) remain limited.

Figure 105 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 9

Question 9 indicates a generally positive perception of sustainability in urban renovation practices, with a majority of responses in the higher range (56.3%), compared to a smaller share at medium level.

Qualitative responses (Question 10) emphasize that sustainability in renovation is highly context-dependent, particularly influenced by building characteristics and execution quality. At the same time, specific material-related concerns are identified, including the overuse of certain solutions such as thermal insulation systems. Positive aspects are also noted, including the role of professional expertise and improving practices, as well as a gradual shift toward higher-quality materials and more careful interventions.

Overall, the results indicate that renovation is perceived as relatively more sustainable than new construction, but remains uneven in practice, depending on technical capacity, material choices, and project-specific conditions.

- “The use of polystyrene for building insulation is too widespread and is not considered the best solution.”
- “Many companies still need to improve their capacity to deliver high-quality construction.”

Figure 106 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 11

For Question 11, responses indicate that recent changes in construction are mainly driven by an increased focus on energy efficiency (37%), followed by higher density (19%) and greater use of prefabricated components (16%). Other trends, such as sustainable materials and return to traditional techniques (9% each), are less prominent, while remaining responses are marginal.

Qualitative responses (Question 12) confirm that the reintroduction of traditional materials and techniques is limited and context-specific. Their use is mainly associated with heritage-related interventions or isolated applications, while their presence in contemporary construction remains minimal. This indicates that recent changes are primarily technical, while the integration of traditional materials and techniques remains selective and not yet structurally embedded in current construction practices.

The results indicate that recent changes are primarily technical (energy efficiency, densification), while the integration of traditional materials and techniques remains selective and not yet structurally embedded in current construction practices.

- “Historical construction styles have been reintroduced in the renovation of buildings in the historic center.”
- “Use of solid wood is mostly limited to decorative and small-scale applications.”

Figure 107 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 13

Question 13 indicates a moderate presence of traditional architectural elements in the urban fabric, with most responses concentrated at a medium level (56.3%), suggesting partial but not systematic integration.

Qualitative responses (Questions 14-15) show that these elements are spatially concentrated, primarily in heritage areas, and are often preserved through renovation rather than integrated into new construction. Their presence in the broader urban fabric remains limited and inconsistent. A key constraint is the dominance of contemporary construction practices, driven by economic and practical factors, which contributes to a lack of coherence and continuity in the architectural expression. At the same time, responses highlight the distinctiveness of local traditions, particularly wood-based architecture, including elements such as wooden houses, churches, gates, and traditional features like the porch. These are recognized as both culturally significant and adaptable to contemporary use, although their integration remains limited.

Overall, the results indicate that traditional architectural elements are present and valued, but fragmented and largely confined to heritage contexts, with unrealized potential for broader integration into contemporary urban development.

- “Most investors prefer modern materials and techniques, which are easier to implement and more cost-efficient.”
- “Traditional architectural elements are mainly present in buildings located in the historic center and adjacent areas.”
- “Traditional timber construction in Maramureş is based on durable techniques using solid wood joinery without metal, wooden shingle roofs, and carved elements, reflecting a strong local identity and offering valuable potential for integration into contemporary sustainable architecture.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 108 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 1

Structural use in both new and renovated buildings receives more balanced evaluations, while non-structural applications, especially exterior and interior finishes, are consistently rated more positively. This pattern is more evident in renovation, where wood is better integrated across applications, while in public space interventions perceptions remain positive but more neutral. The results reflect strong acceptance of wood in design-related uses, alongside a more cautious approach to its structural application.

Figure 109 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 2

Question 2 indicates that the use of wood in urban construction is primarily constrained by technical barriers (56.3%), followed by social and environmental factors (37.5%), and economic and regulatory constraints (31.3%), with additional political and cultural influences (25%).

Qualitative responses (Question 3) indicate that the use of wood is constrained by limited technical capacity, reinforced by concerns related to durability, maintenance, and performance. These are compounded by regulatory constraints and cost-driven market practices, which continue to favor conventional materials.

Question 4 highlights emerging opportunities, particularly related to local resource availability, the potential of prefabricated systems in meeting NZEB requirements, and growing interest in wood-based solutions. Additional opportunities are identified in public space interventions, renovation, and the integration of traditional craftsmanship into contemporary applications.

The results indicate that wood use is limited by structural, regulatory, and perception-based barriers, but supported by clear opportunities linked to local resources, prefabrication, and increasing market openness.

- “The use of wood is limited by strict regulations, especially fire safety requirements and height restrictions.”
- “There is a lack of skilled labor, specialists, and craftsmen for timber construction.”
- “Investors are reluctant to use prefabricated timber solutions due to higher costs.”
- “Public perception remains cautious, with concerns about durability and maintenance.”
- “Prefabricated timber solutions can support compliance with NZEB standards and act as a driver for wider adoption.”
- “Opportunities exist in public projects, especially in urban design and small-scale interventions.”

HERITAGE AND CRAFTSMANSHIP

Historical Construction Practices

Questions 1 and 2 indicate that the historical urban fabric is defined by a layered development, shaped by multiple time periods, from the **Middle Ages and the 17th-19th centuries** to more recent interventions. Architecturally, the responses highlight a combination of **Baroque, Classical, and Neoclassical influences**, alongside **Gothic and Art Nouveau elements**, often adapted to local vernacular contexts. This reflects a heterogeneous urban structure, where successive historical layers coexist within the built environment.

Figure 110 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 3

Figure 111 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

Question 3 indicates that historical construction relied primarily on stone and wood as dominant structural materials, with brick playing a secondary role. This material profile reflects a construction logic based on locally available resources, combining mineral durability with the structural versatility of wood. Question 4 indicates that exterior materials in historical construction were primarily stone and brick, with wood used more selectively. This reflects a material logic focused on durability and protection, based on locally available resources.

Qualitative responses (Question 5) highlight distinctive local construction practices combining materials, techniques, and styles. These include exposed brick and local stone used in façades and plinths, often through mixed masonry, alongside wooden elements in roof structures and decorative details. Architectural expression reflects a local reinterpretation of European styles, combined with vernacular influences, defining a coherent architectural identity shaped by material efficiency, craftsmanship, and local adaptation.

• “The historic center is defined by a combination of exposed red brick, local stone, and carved wood elements, used through mixed masonry techniques and traditional roof structures, reflecting a local reinterpretation of Baroque and Neoclassical styles influenced by vernacular traditions.”

Figure 112 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 7

Figure 113 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 6

Question 6 indicates a generally moderate level of heritage preservation, with responses suggesting variability in how preservation is implemented across different contexts. This distribution points to a situation in which **preservation efforts are present but uneven**, with outcomes varying depending on context and the level of intervention.

Question 7 indicates that heritage buildings are strongly associated with identity and local pride, reflecting a high level of perceived cultural value.

Responses to Question 8 point to a decline in the use of traditional materials and techniques, driven by industrialization and the adoption of modern construction systems. At the same time, Question 9 highlights limited processes of reintroduction, particularly through restoration and context-specific interventions. This contrast reflects a gap between perception and practice, where heritage is highly valued but only selectively integrated into contemporary construction.

- “Industrialization and modern materials have reduced the use of traditional techniques and materials, threatening the continuity of authentic urban heritage, while restoration projects remain essential for their preservation.”
- “Traditional materials such as stone and wood are being selectively reintroduced, mainly through restoration and heritage-related interventions.”

Rural Areas

CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN

Local Construction Practices

Figure 114 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 1

Figure 115 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 2

For Question 1 construction activity in the local rural area is primarily driven by new construction (43.8%), followed by renovation (25%), with a smaller share combining both approaches (12.6%). This distribution reflects a mixed development pattern, combining expansion with interventions on the existing building stock.

For Question 2 construction practices in the local rural area are predominantly based on on-site methods (81.3%), with only limited use of prefabricated components (6.3%). This reflects a largely non-industrialized construction context, with minimal adoption of prefabricated systems.

Figure 116 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 3

Figure 117 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a balanced material use in new construction in rural areas. Structural use is led by wood (29%), followed by concrete (27%) and brick (27%), while stone (12%) and steel (5%) have lower shares. For exterior applications, wood (32%) and brick (30%) are most prevalent, followed by stone (16%) and concrete (14%), with other materials having minor contributions.

Figure 118 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a predominantly moderate perception of sustainability in rural construction practices, with responses concentrated around medium and higher evaluations.

Qualitative responses (Question 6) point to key limiting factors, including economic constraints, limited technical capacity, and the influence of urban construction models on rural practices. At the same time, sustainability is linked to design quality and the integration of appropriate solutions, alongside the need to preserve local building traditions. This reflects a construction context where sustainability remains uneven, shaped by financial constraints, technical capacity, and external influences.

- “Limited financial capacity leads investors to choose low-cost, semi-qualified labor, resulting in less sustainable construction practices.”
- “Urban construction models influence rural areas, reducing the use of traditional practices.”
- “Traditional architecture should be preserved and adapted through renovation rather than replacement.”
- “The architectural concept should integrate sustainable solutions, but the workforce is not trained to apply them.”

Figure 119 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 7

Figure 120 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 8

Questions 7 and 8 indicate a diverse material profile in rural renovation practices. Structural use is dominated by wood (32%), followed by brick (23%), concrete (20%), and stone (18%), while steel (5%) plays a minor role. For exterior applications, wood (37%) and brick (27%) are most prevalent, followed by stone (24%), while glass (5%), metal (2%), and concrete (2%) remain marginal.

Figure 121 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 9

Rural renovation practices are generally perceived as moderately sustainable, with responses concentrated around medium and higher evaluations.

Qualitative responses (Question 10) highlight key constraints, including economic limitations, the overuse of industrial materials, and the weak integration of traditional techniques. These are associated with concerns regarding the loss of architectural identity, suggesting a context where sustainability remains uneven, shaped by cost-driven decisions, material choices, and limited integration of local construction practices.

- “Limited financial capacity leads investors to rely on low-cost, semi-qualified labor, resulting in less sustainable construction practices.”
- “Polystyrene is widely used in rural renovations, often at the expense of more environmentally friendly materials.”
- “Many interventions do not preserve traditional architecture, leading to a loss of local identity.”

Figure 122 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 11

Question 11 highlights a dual trend between modernization and partial reorientation towards traditional practices, driven primarily by increased attention to energy efficiency (56.3%) and, to a lesser extent, the reintroduction of traditional materials and techniques (37.5%). Qualitative responses (Question 12) confirm that traditional practices, particularly wood-based solutions, are being reintroduced, but in a limited and context-specific manner. At the same time, their application remains uneven and not widespread, indicating that while traditional construction knowledge persists, its integration into contemporary rural practices remains fragmented.

- “Solid wood is frequently used as a structural element (blockbau) and in attached elements such as terraces, pergolas, kiosks, and gates.”
- “Wood is used in certain areas, but its overall use remains limited and relatively rare across the territory.”

Figure 123 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 13

Traditional architectural elements in rural areas are generally present at a moderate level, but not consistently integrated. Qualitative responses (Question 14) indicate a dual pattern: while traditional elements are still used in certain contexts, their application is often superficial or inconsistently integrated and increasingly limited.

Responses to Question 15 highlight a strong local construction identity, particularly related to wood, described as unique at national level and characteristic of the Maramureş region. This points to a contrast between strong local potential and inconsistent application, with traditional elements remaining present but insufficiently integrated into current practices.

- “Traditional architectural elements are often used, but sometimes in an incorrect or overly decorative way, while their overall presence is becoming increasingly limited despite a growing need for integration.”
- “The rural area of Maramureş is characterized by unique solid wood construction techniques, recognized at national and international level, reflecting a distinctive way of using wood in architecture.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 124 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 1

The use of wood in rural areas is generally perceived positively across all applications, with stronger acceptance in non-structural uses such as exterior and interior finishes. Structural applications are viewed more cautiously, with more balanced evaluations despite an overall positive perception. A similar pattern is observed in renovation projects, while public space interventions show slightly more neutral responses. This highlights a clear distinction between applications, with wood widely valued for its aesthetic and design qualities, but more cautiously approached as a structural material.

Figure 125 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 2

Barriers affecting the use of wood in rural construction are primarily economic and social (50%), followed by technical constraints (43.8%) and cultural factors (31.3%), while regulatory and environmental aspects are less prominent. Qualitative responses (Question 3) highlight that these barriers are closely linked, combining financial limitations, lack of technical capacity, and limited trust in the material. These are further influenced by external factors such as urban construction models and environmental concerns.

At the same time, Question 4 identifies opportunities related to local resources, skills development, and cultural identity, including the need to improve workforce qualification and the potential of tradition-based construction practices. Additional drivers include affordability and sustainability, as well as sectoral opportunities in areas such as tourism. This reflects a context in which wood use is constrained by economic, technical, and perception-based factors, but supported by strong local resources and cultural potential.

- “Costs are higher and people are reluctant to use wood due to concerns about durability and maintenance.”
- “There is a lack of specialists and training, limiting the capacity for timber construction in rural areas, while improving skills and certified timber products could support wider adoption.”
- “Limited financial and institutional support, combined with the influence of urban construction models, affects the use of wood in rural contexts.”
- “The strong link to tradition and the availability of timber resources represent a potential for expanding its use, although the sector remains underdeveloped.”

HERITAGE AND CRAFTSMANSHIP

Historical Construction Practices

Questions 1 and 2 indicate that the rural historical structure is shaped by a layered evolution, primarily dating from the **17th–19th centuries**, with earlier references reinforcing long-term continuity. Architecturally, the dominant reference is the vernacular Maramureş style, reflecting strong **local traditions and craftsmanship**, complemented by selective influences such as **Gothic and Baroque elements**. This defines a rural built environment grounded in local construction practices, with limited but visible external influences.

Figure 126 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 3

Figure 127 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

For Question 3 historical rural construction relied primarily on stone and wood as core structural materials, with brick playing a secondary role. This reflects a construction system based on locally available resources, combining the durability of stone with the structural role of wood, characteristic of traditional building practices.

For Question 4 exterior materials in historical rural construction were primarily stone, followed by wood and brick. This indicates a material logic based on durability and local availability, where natural materials define both functional performance and architectural expression.

Figure 128 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 5

Figure 129 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 6

For Question 5 heritage preservation in rural areas is generally perceived as moderate, with both well-preserved examples and areas where preservation remains limited. This reflects a fragmented preservation landscape, where outcomes depend on local conditions and individual initiatives.

At the same time, responses to Question 7 indicate a decline in the use of traditional materials and techniques, replaced by industrial and prefabricated solutions. This reflects the impact of modernization on traditional construction practices.

Question 8 highlights a partial reintroduction of these elements, mainly through restoration and identity-driven projects, revealing a gap between strong cultural valuation and limited practical application, with traditional practices increasingly restricted to selective interventions.

- “Solid wood structures and traditional joinery techniques are increasingly replaced by concrete, brick, and prefabricated systems.”
- “Traditional materials such as wooden shingles, local stone, and handmade brick are less used, being replaced by industrial alternatives.”
- “Vernacular architectural elements, such as traditional houses with porches and carved gates, are increasingly replaced by standardized modern constructions.”
- “Industrialization has improved efficiency and reduced costs, but has contributed to the decline of traditional construction practices and rural architectural identity.”

Historical Local Crafts

Figure 130 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 1

Figure 131 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 3

For Question 1 traditional crafts historically practiced in the area include carpentry, stone masonry, metalworking, and textile production, reflecting a diversified craft base supporting both construction and domestic functions. At the same time, **In Question 2**, respondents identify several **distinctive traditional crafts**, mainly **carpentry/wood processing, pottery (Baia Mare ceramic center), and metalworking**. The results point to a **multi-functional craft tradition**, where different trades coexisted and supported the development of a coherent local built environment and cultural identity.

For Question 2 the continuation of traditional crafts shows a mixed pattern, indicating both persistence and decline across different contexts. This suggests that traditional crafts are still practiced, but not consistently sustained, being preserved in certain cases while gradually diminishing in others.

Figure 132 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 4

Traditional crafts play a multi-functional role in the local area, contributing to the economy, cultural heritage preservation, and tourism. They are also linked to education, skills development, and community life, highlighting their role in knowledge transfer and social cohesion.

Figure 133 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 5

Figure 134 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 6

For Question 5 the main challenges in maintaining traditional crafts are related to the dominance of industrial and mass-produced alternatives, which reduce demand for handmade products. Additional constraints include the lack of skilled craftsmen and declining interest in traditional practices, reflecting increasing pressure from modern production systems.

Question 6 indicates that traditional crafts are strongly associated with identity and local pride, reflecting a high level of cultural valuation and a shared recognition of their importance within the community.

Responses to Question 7 indicate a decline in everyday practice, driven by the replacement of traditional techniques and materials with industrial alternatives.

Question 8 highlights processes of selective reintroduction, primarily through cultural, educational, and heritage-oriented initiatives, involving crafts such as wood carving, weaving, and pottery. Question 9 further reinforces this trend, emphasizing the need to support and reintroduce practices related to wood, stone, and metal processing, particularly through initiatives that facilitate knowledge transfer and contemporary adaptation. This points to a transition from functional use to selective and symbolic roles, where traditional crafts remain culturally significant but are no longer consistently embedded in everyday practices.

- “Traditional crafts such as wood carving, weaving, pottery, and metalworking have declined due to industrialization and the replacement of handmade products with faster and cheaper industrial alternatives.”
- “These crafts are based on natural materials and manual techniques, including solid wood processing, textile production, and handcrafted ceramics, reflecting a strong local tradition.”
- “Traditional crafts are being selectively reintroduced through cultural projects, educational workshops, and heritage initiatives, mainly for tourism and symbolic use rather than everyday practice.”

Figure 135 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 10

Figure 136 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 11

The results indicate that traditional crafts are primarily valued for their **political (31%)**, **cultural (23%)**, and **technical (23%)** dimensions, while **economic (15%)** and **social (8%)** aspects are less emphasized. Furthermore, traditional wood crafts show a strong association with local identity and pride, with responses concentrated at the upper end of the scale (**ratings 4 and 5, each 40%**), indicating a high perceived relevance in the local context.

Figure 137 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 12

Figure 138 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Baia Mare: responses to Question 13

For Question 12 traditional wood-related crafts remain actively used, with a majority of respondents (80%) confirming their continued presence, while a smaller share (20%) considers them underutilized. This indicates that, although still relevant, their potential is not fully integrated into current practices.

Question 13 shows that generational differences in the perception of wood are uneven, with contrasting views indicating both continuity and change.

Responses to Question 14 highlight both a break in knowledge transmission and a shift in perception toward aesthetics and cultural value. Question 15 indicates a decline in traditional practices, largely replaced by industrial materials and prefabricated systems. Question 16 highlights underutilized techniques with potential for reintroduction, particularly in sustainable construction and contemporary design. This reflects a transition from loss of practical knowledge toward selective reinterpretation of traditional wood practices.

- “Younger generations are less engaged in traditional crafts, due to migration and declining interest in vocational training.”
- “There is continuity in the appreciation of wood, but the perception has shifted from utility and durability toward aesthetics, ecology, and cultural value.”
- “Traditional wood techniques are increasingly abandoned, but remain underutilized resources with potential for integration into contemporary design, sustainable construction, and cultural tourism.”

4.2. Berlin, Germany

Based on the 7 responses collected, the results for Berlin provide a limited and specialized dataset, reflecting exclusively the perspective of Construction and Design stakeholders, with no input from the Heritage and Craftsmanship group.

BERLIN - BRANDENBURG		
	Urban Areas	Rural Areas
Key challenges affecting the use of wood in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs and limited economic competitiveness compared to concrete and steel systems; • Limited technical expertise and knowledge within both industry and public administration; • Timber construction remains confined to pilot and individual projects, not scaled systemically; • Dominance of conventional materials (concrete, steel) in mainstream construction; • Weak focus on renovation and transformation of existing buildings; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic constraints and cost pressures limit wider adoption of timber solutions; • Existing construction practices change slowly due to lack of incentives; • Limited technical knowledge and access to alternative construction methods; • Regulatory frameworks (e.g. DIN standards) constrain flexibility and innovation; • Perception of wood as less durable continues to affect adoption; • Continued reliance on conventional materials and systems;
Key opportunities for expanding the use of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong potential for scaling timber construction through serial and prefabricated systems; • Policy support, financial incentives, and CO₂ pricing can improve competitiveness; • Better integration of timber in LCA frameworks can support decision-making; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities for timber use in both renovation and new construction contexts; • Strong potential for prefabricated housing and modular systems; • Training and knowledge transfer can significantly improve adoption; • Financial support and policy incentives can unlock wider use;

<p>wood in the construction sector</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public sector commitment to circular construction and natural materials can drive change; • High potential in renovation and transformation of existing building stock; • Increasing interest in alternative materials such as timber, clay, straw, and hemp; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timber construction already recognized and accepted as a traditional material; • Potential to combine traditional practices with modern sustainable solutions;
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Figure 139 Key challenges and opportunities identified based on stakeholders qualitative answers in Berlin

General information

The responses to Question 1 confirm that all 7 participants are active in Berlin and its surrounding area, ensuring a locally grounded and context-relevant dataset. Additionally, 100% of respondents belong to the **“Construction and design - architects, engineers, builders, urban planners, professional associations”** group, with no representation from the **“Heritage and craftsmanship - craftsmen, artisans, heritage experts, cultural institutions, craft schools”** group.

Figure 140 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 4

Regarding Question 4, the distribution of responses indicates a concentrated professional structure across the wood value chain. **Architecture (71.4%)** represents the dominant field, while **wood processing or carpentry and new construction, renovation, and technical building management (each 14.3%)** contribute to a more limited technical base. The absence of other fields such as construction, engineering, and planning reflects a narrower stakeholder composition, primarily oriented toward design-related activities.

Figure 141 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 5

Figure 142 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 7

For Question 5, the results indicate a relatively low level of institutionalized collaboration within the wood value chain, with **71% of respondents not engaged in any cluster or association**, compared to 29% who are involved in such structures. As reflected in Question 6, existing collaborations are limited to a small number of actors, including **Landesbeirat Holz Berlin Brandenburg, B4 Netzwerk, and the Architektenkammer Berlin**, suggesting a still fragmented but partially connected network.

Question 7 indicates that **most projects are located either in both urban and rural areas (57%) or exclusively in urban areas (43%)**, with no responses indicating a solely rural focus. This distribution reflects a strong urban orientation, while also highlighting the involvement of stakeholders in projects that extend beyond the city boundaries.

Urban Areas
CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN
Local construction practices

Figure 143 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 1

Figure 144 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 2

Question 1 indicates that **new construction** is the most frequent project type in the local urban area (**71%**), followed by both renovation and renovation with extension (**each 14%**), while a small share of respondents are uncertain (**14%**). This distribution highlights a strong focus on new development, with more limited involvement in interventions on the existing building stock.

Question 2 shows that construction practices in the local urban area are characterized by a significant level of uncertainty (**57%**), while on-site construction methods account for **28%** and limited use of prefabricated components for **14%**. No responses indicate an extensive use of prefabrication. This pattern suggests a low level of clarity or consistency in construction approaches, alongside a limited adoption of industrialized building methods.

Figure 145 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 3

Figure 146 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a relatively diversified material profile in the local urban construction sector, without a clear dominance of a single structural material. Concrete (33%), wood (33%), and brick (27%) show comparable shares, suggesting a **mixed construction logic that integrates both conventional and alternative materials**, while steel remains marginal (7%).

A different pattern emerges for exterior materials, where wood becomes the dominant solution (44%), followed by concrete (22%) and a dispersed use of other materials (each 11%). This shift highlights a stronger positioning of **wood in non-structural applications**, indicating its higher acceptance in design-related uses, while its structural role remains more balanced within the overall material mix.

Figure 147 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a moderate perception of sustainability in current urban construction practices, with most responses concentrated at lower to medium levels and a smaller share reflecting more positive evaluations.

Qualitative responses (Question 6) highlight several structural constraints affecting sustainability. A key issue is the continued dominance of conventional construction systems, particularly concrete and steel, alongside a limited integration of wood. Timber-based solutions, including timber panel façade elements or hybrid systems, are mainly applied in pilot or individual projects and are not yet widely adopted. This reflects a gap between innovative construction approaches and mainstream

practices, where sustainable solutions remain isolated rather than systemic. At the same time, development trends continue to focus on new construction, while the transformation of the existing building stock remains insufficiently addressed, further limiting sustainability outcomes. Overall, the results indicate a partial and uneven integration of sustainability, shaped by material choices, development practices, and the limited scaling of innovative solutions, while also pointing to opportunities related to timber construction and more systemic approaches to sustainable building.

- “The share of wood in construction remains low, with most buildings still based on concrete structures.”
- “Innovative timber construction is currently limited to pilot and individual projects, while large-scale adoption is still dominated by conventional materials such as concrete and steel.”
- “There is a need to shift focus from new construction toward the transformation of the existing building stock.”

Figure 148 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 7

Figure 149 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 8

Questions 7 and 8 indicate that renovation practices are characterized by a diversified material profile, with a stronger integration of wood compared to new construction. Structural use is dominated by wood (40%), followed by concrete (20%) and steel (13%), while other materials have marginal shares.

A similar pattern is observed for exterior materials, where wood is dominant (44%), followed by concrete (22%) and a dispersed use of other materials. This suggests a higher level of material diversification and a stronger role of wood in renovation practices.

Figure 150 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 9

Question 9 indicates a moderate perception of sustainability in urban renovation practices, with most responses concentrated at a medium level (57.1%), followed by lower (28.6%) and higher evaluations (14.3%).

Qualitative responses (Question 10) highlight constraints related to material choices, particularly the continued use of conventional products and the limited adoption of sustainable materials due to higher costs. At the same time, concerns are raised regarding the environmental impact of petroleum-based insulation, while references to historical constructions suggest potential for more sustainable approaches.

Overall, the results indicate that renovation is perceived as relatively sustainable, but remains constrained by cost-driven decisions and material-related limitations.

- “Renovation is generally considered sustainable, although petroleum-based insulation materials have a negative impact.”
- “Sustainable materials, such as bio-based insulation, are not widely used due to higher costs.”
- “Construction continues to rely mainly on conventional materials, with limited adoption of alternative solutions.”

Figure 151 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 11

Question 11 indicates that recent changes in the local urban construction sector reflect a transition toward more diversified drivers, with no single dominant trend. Energy efficiency, sustainable materials, and prefabrication show similar shares, alongside a slightly higher emphasis on densification, suggesting a combined technical and regulatory shift rather than a clear material transition.

Qualitative responses (Question 12) highlight that the integration of bio-based and traditional materials (e.g. clay, straw, hemp, timber) remains limited and largely confined to pilot or experimental projects, indicating a gap between emerging innovation and mainstream construction practices.

The results suggest that current changes are still primarily incremental, with alternative materials not yet scaled or structurally embedded in the sector.

- “Materials such as clay, straw, and hemp are used mainly in pilot or model projects, not at a large scale.”
- “There is growing interest in using clay as a construction material, including in projects currently in planning.”
- “Timber construction is also recognized as a relevant alternative, but not yet widely implemented.”

Figure 152 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 13

Question 13 indicates a moderate to high presence of traditional architectural elements, with responses concentrated at medium to higher levels (3-4), suggesting partial but consistent integration. Qualitative responses (Questions 14-15) indicate that these elements are mainly embedded in the existing building stock, while their integration into contemporary construction remains limited and mostly experimental. At the same time, current practices emphasize prefabrication and modern materials, with only selective reinterpretations of traditional systems.

Overall, the results indicate a structural continuity at the level of the existing built environment, but a limited translation into current construction practices.

- “Berlin is largely characterized by a hybrid construction system combining brick and wood.”
- “Historic buildings, especially Gründerzeit housing, retain traditional elements such as wooden floors, roof structures, and decorative façades.”
- “Traditional architectural elements are still present, but there is limited transfer of historical construction practices into contemporary architecture.”
- “The urban structure is defined by block perimeter development with consistent building heights, reflecting a strong historical pattern.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 153 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 1

Question 1 indicates a generally positive perception of wood in urban construction, varying by application. The structure of new buildings records the highest positive responses, while exterior finishes of new buildings and interior finishes or furniture in new buildings are also rated mainly positive. In contrast, the structure of renovated buildings and interior finishes or furniture in renovated buildings show higher neutral responses. Lower and more mixed evaluations appear for exterior finishes of renovated buildings and interventions in public space.

Figure 154 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 2

Question 2 indicates that the use of wood in urban construction is primarily constrained by legislative/regulatory barriers (85.7%), followed by technical (71.4%) and economic and political factors (each 57.1%), with cultural aspects and fire safety concerns playing a secondary role (14.3%).

Qualitative responses (Question 3) reinforce these findings, highlighting structural constraints related to regulatory complexity, particularly in fire safety approvals, limited institutional support, and high costs associated with timber construction. These are further compounded by limited technical knowledge and entrenched construction practices favoring conventional materials.

Question 4 highlights emerging opportunities linked to policy support, economic instruments, and scaling mechanisms. Key aspects include the role of public support and funding, CO₂ pricing, and the potential of serial or prefabricated construction to reduce costs. At the same time, a stronger commitment from public authorities toward circular construction and natural materials, alongside improved LCA positioning of timber compared to conventional materials, is identified as a critical enabling factor.

The results indicate that wood use is primarily limited by regulatory, technical, and economic constraints, but could be significantly supported through policy alignment, financial incentives, and the scaling of timber-based construction systems.

- “High costs, limited expertise, and regulatory complexity, especially regarding fire safety, remain key barriers to timber construction.”
- “There is insufficient support from public institutions, alongside limited knowledge within both administration and the construction sector.”
- “Clear policy support, financial incentives, and better integration of timber in LCA frameworks could significantly increase adoption.”
- “Cost reductions through standardized and serial construction approaches could support wider implementation of timber systems.”

**Rural Areas
CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN
Local Construction Practices**

Figure 155 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 1

Figure 156 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 2

Question 1 indicates a balanced distribution between new construction and renovation (each 42.9%), suggesting no clear dominance of expansion over intervention-based development in the rural context. Question 2 reflects a transitional construction model, with an equal share of on-site methods and limited prefabrication (each 42.9%), and no adoption of extensive prefabrication. This points to an intermediate stage of industrialization, where conventional practices persist alongside emerging, but not yet consolidated, prefabricated approaches.

Figure 157 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 3

Figure 158 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a mixed use of materials in new rural construction, with no clear dominant material. Wood, stone, and brick are used in similar shares, suggesting that traditional and conventional materials are used together rather than following a single approach. A similar pattern is observed for exterior materials, where brick has a slightly higher share but remains part of a varied material mix. This points to a hybrid construction model, without a clear direction in material use.

Figure 159 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a moderate perception of sustainability in rural construction practices, with responses mainly concentrated at medium levels and a smaller share of higher evaluations. Qualitative responses (Question 6) highlight a mixed situation. On one hand, construction remains largely traditional, with wood accepted as a familiar material and smaller-scale interventions seen as potentially more sustainable. On the other hand, practices are still influenced by conventional materials, limited technical knowledge, and the use of interior materials with negative environmental impacts. The results indicate uneven sustainability, shaped by traditional practices, limited knowledge, and the continued use of conventional solutions.

- “Wood is generally recognized and accepted as a traditional building material, especially in rural contexts where construction practices remain largely traditional.”
- “Construction tends to rely on conventional materials, despite a potentially more sustainable, small-scale approach in rural areas.”
- “There is limited knowledge about material impacts, while interior materials with harmful emissions are still widely used.”

Figure 160 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 7

Figure 161 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 8

Questions 7 and 8 indicate a mixed material profile in rural renovation practices, without a single dominant material. Structural use is led by wood (25%), followed by concrete, stone, and brick (each 18%), with smaller shares for steel, ETICS, and uncertain responses (each 6%). This suggests a

combination of traditional and conventional materials in renovation. A similar pattern is observed for exterior materials, where plaster (28%) and brick (14%) are most used, alongside wood, glass, and metal (each 14%), and smaller shares for stone and ETICS (each 7%). This reflects a varied material mix, indicating no clear dominance of traditional materials in exterior applications.

Figure 162 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 9

Question 9 indicates a moderate perception of sustainability in rural renovation practices, with responses mainly concentrated at medium levels.

Qualitative responses (Question 10) highlight a mixed context, combining traditional practices with the continued use of conventional materials and systems, alongside limited knowledge of alternative solutions. The results indicate uneven sustainability, without a clear shift toward more sustainable practices.

- “Renovation is generally considered a sustainable approach, especially in rural areas where construction remains largely traditional and small-scale.”
- “Construction practices are still focused on conventional, growth-oriented models.”
- “Insulation systems are typically based on glued mineral materials, while knowledge about alternative solutions remains limited.”

Figure 163 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 11

Question 11 indicates that recent changes in rural construction are primarily driven by increased focus on energy efficiency (42.9%) and sustainable materials (28.6%), with more limited influence from prefabrication and densification (each 14.3%). The return to traditional materials is not identified as a significant trend.

Qualitative responses (Question 12) confirm that changes are uneven, with limited evidence of a systematic shift. While timber construction is emerging, most practices remain based on

conventional systems, and the reintroduction of traditional approaches is minimal. The results indicate that changes are mainly technical, with no clear transition toward traditional or alternative construction models.

- “Construction is still dominated by conventional systems, such as brick or stone combined with external insulation systems.”
- “Timber construction is emerging, but its use remains limited.”
- “There is limited knowledge about alternative construction approaches.”

To what extent are traditional architectural elements present in buildings or public spaces in the local rural area?

Figure 164 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 13

Question 13 indicates a moderate presence of traditional architectural elements in rural areas, with responses concentrated at medium levels.

Qualitative responses (Question 14) indicate that these elements are mainly linked to the existing building stock and depend on preservation practices, while their current use remains limited.

Responses to Question 15 highlight the persistence of traditional typologies alongside the continued use of conventional materials, indicating coexistence rather than integration.

Overall, the results indicate that traditional elements are present, but not consistently integrated into current construction practices.

- “Renovation is strongly linked to the existing building stock and influenced by local preservation policies, with higher levels of vacancy in rural areas.”
- “Construction is still dominated by traditional typologies, such as brick masonry, historic farmsteads, and timber-framed buildings.”
- “Timber construction is present but still underutilized in comparison to conventional materials.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 165 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 1

The use of wood is generally perceived positively, with variations depending on the application. The structure of renovated buildings records the highest positive responses, followed by exterior finishes of new buildings and interior finishes or furniture in new buildings. In contrast, interior finishes or furniture in renovated buildings and interventions in public space show higher neutral responses. Lower and more mixed evaluations appear for exterior finishes of renovated buildings, where both negative and very positive responses are present.

Figure 166 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Berlin: responses to Question 2

The use of wood in rural construction is limited by a set of interrelated barriers, with economic factors playing a leading role, followed by technical and regulatory constraints, while cultural aspects are less influential.

Qualitative responses (Question 3) indicate that these challenges stem from cost pressures, existing regulatory frameworks, and the persistence of established construction practices, alongside ongoing concerns about the performance and durability of wood.

At the same time, Question 4 highlights enabling factors such as financial support, improved access to knowledge and training, and the development of prefabricated solutions. This suggests that while current conditions constrain wider adoption, there is potential for expansion through targeted support measures and increased technical capacity.

- “Cultural perceptions of wood as less durable, combined with regulatory constraints (e.g. DIN standards), continue to limit its wider use.”
- “Existing construction practices are slow to change due to a lack of incentives and limited knowledge in the sector.”
- “Opportunities lie in training, knowledge transfer, and policy support, particularly in renovation, new construction, and the prefabricated housing sector.”

4.3. Siena, Italy

Based on the 19 responses collected, the results for Siena reflect a specialized and heritage-oriented dataset, dominated by the Heritage and Craftsmanship group (16 responses), with limited representation from Construction and Design stakeholders (3 responses).

SIENA - TUSCANY		
	Urban Areas	Rural Areas
Key challenges affecting the use of wood in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong dominance of brick and concrete limits the adoption of timber solutions; • Regulatory constraints in historic and UNESCO areas restrict the use of alternative materials and systems; • Technical (75%) and cultural (68.8%) barriers strongly influence material choices; • Wood is perceived as context-specific and less suitable for structural and façade applications; • Weak local supply chains, high costs, and maintenance concerns reduce competitiveness; • Limited innovation and reliance on traditional construction practices slow down transition; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical (32%) and economic (26%) constraints limit the use of timber solutions; • Strong regulatory frameworks restrict flexibility and innovation in construction practices; • Wood is mainly used in small-scale or secondary applications, not as a primary structural system; • Cultural inertia and established construction traditions reduce openness to timber solutions; • Lack of skilled labor and training further limits adoption; • High maintenance requirements reduce attractiveness compared to conventional materials;
Key opportunities for expanding the use of wood in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong potential in renovation, where wood is already used in roofs and finishes; • High demand for energy efficiency (57%) supports integration of timber solutions; • Public projects and small-scale interventions offer entry points for timber use; • Opportunities to combine traditional materials with modern techniques; • Gradual integration of timber in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong regulatory framework ensures continuity of local materials and identity; • Opportunities to expand timber use in annexes, agricultural buildings, and small-scale structures; • Training and skills development can significantly increase timber adoption; • Potential to adapt traditional practices to contemporary sustainable construction; • Improved supply chains and policy support can enable wider use of

	structural applications through pilot projects;	timber; • Integration of wood in landscape-sensitive and heritage-compatible interventions;
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Figure 167 Key challenges and opportunities identified based on stakeholders qualitative answers in Baia Mare

General information

The responses to Question 1 confirm that all 19 participants are active in Siena and its surrounding area, ensuring a locally grounded and context-relevant dataset. Additionally, **84.2%** of respondents belong to the **“Heritage and craftsmanship - craftsmen, artisans, heritage experts, cultural institutions, craft schools”** group, while **15.8%** are part of the **“Construction and design - architects, engineers, builders, urban planners, professional associations”** group.

Figure 168 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

Regarding Question 4, the distribution of responses indicates a diversified and interdisciplinary stakeholder structure, with **architecture as the main field (31.6%)**. This is complemented by **renovation or restoration and planning (each 16.1%)**, while the remaining fields contribute with smaller shares. The profile reflects a multi-sectoral composition oriented toward heritage, design, and territorial processes rather than a purely technical construction focus.

Figure 169 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 5

Figure 170 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 7

For Question 5, the results indicate a high level of institutionalized collaboration within the wood value chain, with **89% of respondents engaged in clusters or associations**, and only 11% not involved. As reflected in Question 6, collaborations include actors such as **FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) and PEFC (Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification)**, as well as **professional associations**, suggesting a relatively well-connected network structure. Question 7 indicates that most projects are located in **both urban and rural areas (53%)**, followed by exclusively **urban areas (42%)**, with a limited share in **rural-only contexts (5%)**. This distribution reflects a territorially integrated scope of activity, extending across both urban and non-urban contexts.

Urban Areas
CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN
Local construction practices

Figure 171 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 1

Figure 172 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 2

Question 1 indicates that renovation is the dominant project type in the local urban area (88%), with only a small share of new construction and mixed projects (each 6%). This distribution reflects a strong focus on interventions within the existing building stock rather than expansion. Question 2 shows that construction practices are primarily based on on-site methods (81%), with limited use of prefabricated components (19%) and no extensive adoption. This pattern indicates a continued reliance on conventional construction approaches, with low uptake of industrialized building systems.

Figure 173 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 3

Figure 174 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a material profile still largely oriented toward conventional solutions. Structural systems are dominated by brick (42%) and wood (21%), followed by smaller shares of steel (8%) and other materials, suggesting a combination of traditional and standard construction materials. A similar pattern is observed for exterior materials, where brick (28%) and concrete (25%) are most used, followed by steel (25%) and wood (15%), with limited presence of other materials. This reflects a material structure where conventional solutions remain prevalent, while wood is present but not dominant across applications.

Figure 175 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a predominantly moderate perception of sustainability in current urban construction practices, with responses concentrated at medium levels (56.3%), suggesting the absence of a strongly consolidated sustainability model.

Qualitative responses (Question 6) highlight structural constraints related to the persistence of traditional construction methods and the continued use of conventional materials, particularly concrete. Sustainability is often associated with energy performance rather than material choice, while cost factors limit the adoption of more sustainable solutions. At the same time, regulatory frameworks and local context, especially in historic areas, constrain the use of innovative materials and techniques.

Overall, the results indicate a transitional context, where sustainability is acknowledged but remains unevenly integrated, shaped by economic constraints, regulatory conditions, and prevailing construction practices.

- “Construction practices remain largely traditional, with limited innovation and generally low sustainability performance.”
- “Sustainability is mainly associated with energy efficiency standards rather than material choice or construction processes.”
- “Costs limit the adoption of more sustainable materials, leading to the continued dominance of conventional solutions such as concrete.”
- “In historic areas, regulatory frameworks require the use of traditional materials, limiting the integration of innovative solutions.”

Figure 176 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 7

Figure 177 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 8

Questions 7 and 8 indicate that renovation practices rely on a mixed material profile. Structural use is dominated by wood (28%) and brick (26%), followed by concrete (21%) and steel (18%), while stone (8%) plays a minor role. For exterior applications, brick (50%) and stone (31%) are predominant, whereas wood (9%), glass (6%), and metal (3%) remain less frequently used.

Figure 178 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 9

Question 9 indicates a predominantly moderate perception of sustainability in urban renovation practices, with responses concentrated at medium levels (68.8%), suggesting the absence of a clearly defined sustainability approach.

Qualitative responses (Question 10) indicate that sustainability is strongly conditioned by traditional construction practices and regulatory frameworks, particularly in historic contexts, where material use is constrained by planning instruments. At the same time, the continued reliance on conventional materials, especially concrete, and the limited integration of wood beyond specific uses (e.g. roof restoration) reflect a narrow application of sustainable solutions. Although natural materials such as stone and brick are recognized, their use does not translate into a systemic shift toward sustainability. The results indicate that renovation is not structurally more sustainable, but rather context-dependent, shaped by regulatory constraints, material choices, and limited innovation.

- “Renovation practices remain largely traditional and are strongly constrained by regulatory frameworks, limiting the use of alternative techniques.”
- “Wood is mainly used in renovation for roof structures and finishes, with limited application in other elements.”
- “Sustainability remains moderate, with continued reliance on conventional materials such as concrete, influenced by cost factors and logistical constraints.”

Have you observed any recent changes in the way buildings are constructed or renovated in the local urban area?

Figure 179 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 11

Question 11 indicates that recent changes in the local urban construction sector are primarily driven by energy efficiency (57%) and, to a lesser extent, by the use of sustainable materials (36%), while other drivers remain marginal.

Qualitative responses (Question 12) indicate that the integration of traditional materials and techniques is limited and largely constrained to specific contexts, particularly in historic areas, where their use is often regulated rather than driven by innovation. The continued reliance on industrial products, alongside isolated references to materials such as lime or brick, suggests a selective and non-systemic use of traditional solutions. The results indicate that recent changes are primarily technical, with limited evidence of a structural transition toward alternative or tradition-based construction models.

- “In historic areas, traditional materials such as lime-based plasters continue to be used, often within industrial production systems.”
- “Interventions are strongly influenced by heritage regulations, which guide material choices rather than reflecting a return to traditional construction practices.”
- “Construction combines modern techniques with the selective use of traditional materials, without a full integration of traditional systems.”

To what extent are traditional architectural elements present in buildings or urban spaces in your city?

Figure 180 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 13

Question 13 indicates a high presence of traditional architectural elements in the urban fabric, with responses concentrated at higher levels (4 - 5), suggesting a strong and consistent integration.

Qualitative responses (Questions 14 -15) indicate that this presence is structurally embedded, particularly in the historic center, where regulatory frameworks enforce the use of traditional materials and architectural language. At the same time, this integration is uneven, with peripheral areas showing a shift toward conventional construction practices and reduced architectural coherence. The results indicate a strong continuity of traditional architecture in regulated contexts, contrasted by a more fragmented and less controlled expression outside heritage areas.

- “Traditional architectural elements, such as exposed brick, stone, arches, and vaulted structures, are widely present, especially in the historic center.”
- “Strong regulatory frameworks, particularly in the UNESCO-listed areas, enforce the use of traditional materials and architectural continuity.”
- “While historic areas maintain a strong traditional identity, peripheral areas are characterized by more conventional and less coherent construction practices.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 181 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 1

The structure of new and renovated buildings and interior finishes or furniture in renovated buildings record the highest positive responses, followed by interior finishes in new buildings. In contrast, exterior finishes show more neutral responses, while interventions in public space present more mixed evaluations.

Figure 182 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 2

Question 2 indicates that the use of wood in urban construction is primarily constrained by technical barriers (75%) and cultural factors (68.8%), followed by economic constraints (43.8%), while regulatory and political aspects have a more limited influence.

Qualitative responses (Question 3) indicate that these barriers are linked to limited technical capacity, weak local supply chains, and persistent cultural perceptions of wood as a context-specific or less durable material. These are reinforced by maintenance concerns and the dominance of alternative construction traditions based on brick and stone.

Question 4 highlights opportunities related to skills development, improved supply and distribution systems, and the gradual introduction of wood in public projects, particularly in small-scale interventions, public spaces, and new construction. At the same time, its use in structural applications is seen as having potential, while exterior applications remain more constrained by local traditions. The results indicate that wood use is primarily limited by technical, cultural, and systemic factors, but supported by opportunities linked to public sector involvement, training, and gradual market adoption.

- “Wood is still perceived as suitable only for specific contexts, with limited integration in structural or façade applications due to cultural and technical constraints.”
- “Limited local supply, high costs, and maintenance requirements, combined with weak supply chains, restrict the wider use of timber.”
- “Lack of training and professional expertise further limits confidence in timber construction.”
- “Opportunities exist in public projects, small-scale interventions, and structural applications, where wood could be gradually introduced and expanded.”

HERITAGE AND CRAFTSMANSHIP

Historical Construction Practices

Questions 1 and 2 indicate that the historical urban fabric is predominantly defined by **medieval development**, with consistent references to the **Middle Ages as the main period of formation**. This is complemented by later insertions, particularly from the **18th and 19th centuries**, alongside limited more recent interventions. Architecturally, the responses suggest a relatively homogeneous structure, characterized by traditional masonry construction and strong historical continuity, with later additions integrated into the existing urban fabric rather than redefining it.

Figure 183 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 3

Figure 184 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate that historical construction relied on a limited and consistent material palette, with brick and stone as the dominant materials, reflecting a construction logic based on durable and locally available resources, used both structurally and for exterior applications. Qualitative responses (Question 5) provide limited and non-specific detail, indicating a low level of articulated recognition of distinctive construction practices. While one response highlights the use of local materials such as travertine, others refer only generally to structural materials or indicate the absence of distinctive elements.

- “Travertine, as a locally recognized material, can be considered one of the few distinctive elements, although references to unique construction practices remain limited.”

Figure 185 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 6

Figure 186 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 7

Question 6 indicates a relatively high level of heritage preservation, with responses distributed between medium and high levels (3-5), suggesting generally consistent preservation practices, although not uniformly applied.

Question 7 indicates a very strong association between heritage buildings and local identity, with all responses concentrated at the highest level, reflecting a consolidated perception of cultural value. Responses to Question 8 indicate a limited but identifiable decline in the use of traditional materials and techniques, with inconsistent responses suggesting low consensus. At the same time, Question

9 highlights a fragmented and non-systemic process of reintroduction, limited to isolated materials such as brick and bio-based solutions. This contrast reflects a clear alignment in perception but a weaker translation into practice, with heritage strongly valued but only partially integrated into contemporary construction.

• “Wood and brick are used, and in some cases bio-based construction is also present, although not consistently.”

Rural Areas
CONSTRUCTION AND DESIGN
Local Construction Practices

Figure 187 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 1

Figure 188 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 2

Question 1 indicates that construction activity in the local rural area is predominantly oriented toward renovation (87.4%), with only marginal shares for new construction and uncertain responses. This suggests a strong focus on interventions within the existing building stock rather than expansion.

Question 2 indicates that construction practices are primarily based on on-site methods (75%), with limited use of prefabricated components (25%) and no extensive adoption. This reflects a predominantly non-industrialized construction context, with low integration of prefabricated systems.

Figure 189 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 3

Figure 190 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate a diversified material structure in new rural construction, without a single dominant solution. Structural use is led by brick (30%) and steel (24%), followed by concrete (22%), while wood (11%) and stone (13%) play secondary roles. A similar pattern is observed for exterior materials, where brick (36%) remains the most used, followed by stone (29%), with wood (11%) and concrete (11%) having more limited shares. This suggests a mixed material logic, where conventional solutions remain prevalent, with limited dominance of traditional materials such as wood.

Figure 191 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 5

Question 5 indicates a predominantly moderate perception of sustainability in rural construction practices, with responses concentrated at medium levels (75%), suggesting the absence of a clearly defined sustainability approach.

Qualitative responses (Question 6) indicate that sustainability is constrained by the persistence of traditional construction practices, regulatory limitations, and the continued use of conventional materials, particularly concrete-based systems. At the same time, sustainability is influenced by low levels of innovation, limited integration of renewable solutions, and weak alignment with environmental context, with additional constraints related to waste management and resource use. The results indicate a low and uneven level of sustainability, shaped by regulatory frameworks, material choices, and limited adoption of alternative or nature-based solutions.

- “Construction practices remain largely traditional, with limited innovation and generally low sustainability performance.”
- “New constructions are predominantly based on concrete structures with brick infill, influenced by regulatory constraints and established building practices.”
- “Sustainability remains limited, with low adoption of renewable energy and nature-based solutions, particularly in rural areas.”

Figure 192 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 7

Figure 193 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 8

Questions 7 and 8 indicate a diversified material structure in rural renovation, without a single dominant material. Structural use is led by steel (28%) and wood (23%), followed by brick (21%) and concrete (17%), while stone has a more limited role (11%), suggesting a mixed use of conventional and traditional materials. A different pattern is observed for exterior materials, where brick becomes dominant (35%), followed by stone (19%), while other materials, including steel and glass (each 12%), and wood (8%), have secondary roles. This indicates that exterior solutions remain more strongly anchored in conventional material choices, despite a diversified structural base.

Figure 194 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 9

Question 9 reflects a predominantly moderate perception of sustainability in rural renovation practices, with responses concentrated at medium levels (68.8%), indicating the lack of a clearly established sustainability model.

Qualitative responses (Question 10) indicate that sustainability is conditioned by regulatory frameworks and the persistence of traditional construction practices, particularly in relation to material use. While regulations enforce the use of local and traditional materials, this does not necessarily translate into higher sustainability performance, as conventional solutions and limited innovation remain prevalent. At the same time, economic constraints and low use of renewable materials further limit the adoption of more advanced sustainable approaches. The results point to a context where sustainability is regulated but not structurally optimized, shaped by compliance requirements, material choices, and limited integration of innovative or high-performance solutions.

- “Construction practices remain largely traditional, with limited innovation and generally moderate sustainability performance.”
- “Strong regulatory frameworks impose the use of local and traditional materials (such as stone, brick, and lime), ensuring landscape integration but limiting alternative solutions.”
- “The use of renewable materials and high-performance solutions remains limited, often requiring additional interventions to meet thermal and sustainability standards.”

Have you observed any recent changes in the way buildings are constructed or renovated in your local rural area?

Figure 195 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 11

Question 11 reflects a predominantly technical orientation of recent changes in rural construction, driven mainly by increased attention to energy efficiency (51.6%) and, to a lesser extent, the use of sustainable materials (32.3%), while other drivers remain marginal.

Qualitative responses (Question 12) indicate that the integration of traditional materials and techniques is limited and inconsistent. While some references point to the continued use or partial reintroduction of materials such as brick or lime, most responses suggest continuity rather than transformation, with traditional practices maintained rather than actively reintroduced.

- “Traditional construction practices have never been completely abandoned and are largely maintained in rural areas.”
- “There is a tendency to preserve historic construction styles, rather than actively reintroduce them.”
- “Some limited material substitutions are observed, such as replacing cement with lime or the continued use of brick.”

To what extent are traditional architectural elements present in buildings or public spaces in the local rural area?

Figure 196 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 13

Question 13 indicates a strong presence of traditional architectural elements in rural areas, with responses concentrated at higher levels, suggesting consistent integration within the built environment.

Qualitative responses (Question 14) indicate that traditional elements are systematically maintained, supported by regulatory frameworks and established construction practices, with widespread use of traditional materials and typologies.

Responses to Question 15 confirm the persistence of a coherent local construction identity, based on recurring use of masonry, brick, and stone, and reinforced by conservation-oriented approaches. The results indicate a stable and well-integrated traditional framework, with limited variation or reinterpretation in contemporary construction practices.

- “Construction practices are generally low in innovation, being strongly influenced by both cultural factors and strict regulatory frameworks.”
- “Traditional architectural elements and materials, such as exposed brick, stone, and timber details, are widely preserved and consistently integrated, especially in rural typologies like farmsteads.”
- “Strong landscape and heritage regulations enforce the preservation of traditional forms, materials, and typologies, limiting flexibility but ensuring a high level of architectural coherence.”

Use of Wood in Construction

Figure 197 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 1

Question 1 shows a generally positive perception of wood across most applications, with the highest values for the structure of new buildings, interior finishes in new buildings, and structure of renovated buildings. In contrast, exterior finishes of renovated buildings show more neutral responses, while interventions in public space are more mixed.

The use of wood in rural construction is constrained by a combination of factors, with technical (32.4%) and economic barriers (26.5%) playing a leading role, followed by cultural constraints (20.6%), while other factors remain marginal.

Figure 198 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 2

Qualitative responses (Question 3) indicate that these barriers are shaped by regulatory restrictions, cultural inertia, and limited technical capacity. Strong planning constraints in rural areas limit flexibility, while maintenance requirements and the lack of skilled labor further reduce the attractiveness of wood as a material.

Question 4 highlights opportunities related to skills development, regulatory adaptation, and the gradual expansion of wood use in smaller-scale applications, such as agricultural buildings, annexes, and outdoor structures. Broader adoption is also linked to improved material supply and increased openness from both professionals and policymakers. The results point to a constrained but evolving context, where systemic barriers persist, but opportunities emerge through training, regulatory adjustments, and diversification of applications.

- “Expanding training for professionals and public authorities could significantly increase the use of timber in construction.”
- “Wood is mainly used in small-scale applications, such as agricultural structures, annexes, and outdoor elements, with limited use in main buildings.”
- “Cultural and regulatory constraints limit the adoption of innovative timber solutions, with strict frameworks restricting alternative approaches.”
- “High maintenance requirements and the lack of skilled craftsmen further reduce the attractiveness of timber construction.”

HERITAGE AND CRAFTSMANSHIP

Historical Construction Practices

Questions 1 and 2 indicate that the rural historical structure is predominantly defined by medieval development, with consistent references to the **Middle Ages and the Renaissance**, suggesting strong temporal continuity. Architecturally, the responses highlight a vernacular rural typology based on traditional farmhouses, rooted in medieval layouts and later adapted through subsequent interventions. This reflects a coherent rural structure, shaped by long-term continuity and gradual transformation rather than distinct stylistic shifts.

Figure 199 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 3

Figure 200 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

Questions 3 and 4 indicate that historical rural construction is based on a limited and consistent material palette, dominated by stone (40-50%) and brick (33-40%), with wood (20%) playing a secondary role. This pattern is consistent across both structural and exterior applications, suggesting a construction logic grounded in durable, locally available materials, with limited variation between structural systems and façade treatments.

Figure 201 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 5

Figure 202 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 6

Question 5 reflects a high level of heritage preservation in rural areas, with all responses concentrated at the highest level (100%), indicating a strong and consistent conservation of the built heritage.

Responses to Question 7 indicate a limited and inconsistent perception of decline in traditional materials and techniques, with references to wood alongside non-specific or absent responses, suggesting low consensus. At the same time, Question 8 highlights a similarly fragmented pattern of reintroduction, with isolated references to materials such as wood and brick, alongside negative responses. The results point to a strong preservation framework, but a weak and non-systemic dynamic in the evolution of traditional construction practices.

• “Wood and brick are used in some cases, while in other situations no traditional materials are identified.”

Historical Local Crafts

Figure 203 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 1

Figure 204 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 3

Question 1 indicates a diversified base of traditional crafts, including carpentry, stone masonry, and textile-related activities, suggesting a multi-functional craft system supporting both construction and local production.

Qualitative responses (Question 2) highlight a similarly diversified but more selective recognition of distinctive crafts, with references to **wood processing, metalworking, ceramics, and artisanal production (e.g. jewelry, leather, wool)**. This points to a broad craft tradition, but without a clearly dominant specialization.

Question 3 reflects a moderate level of continuity, with responses concentrated at medium levels (100%), indicating that traditional crafts persist but are not strongly consolidated. The results indicate the presence of a diversified but weakly sustained craft system, characterized by continuity without clear expansion or specialization.

Figure 205 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 4

In the local context, traditional crafts are unevenly integrated, being mainly linked to cultural heritage and tourism, with limited connections to the economy, education, or community activities.

Figure 206 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 5

Figure 207 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 6

In the local context, traditional crafts are under pressure from structural changes, with key challenges linked to industrial competition, lack of skilled craftsmen, and reduced cultural relevance, each accounting for 33.3%. At the same time, perception remains strongly positive, with responses polarized between low and high evaluations, indicating uneven but still significant cultural recognition.

Responses to Questions 7-9 indicate a clear decline in everyday use, driven by the replacement of traditional practices with mass-produced alternatives, while reintroduction processes remain selective and limited. References to materials such as wood and stone, alongside broader calls for reintroducing traditional crafts, suggest a shift toward symbolic and heritage-based roles rather than functional integration. This points to a transition where traditional crafts retain cultural value but are no longer consistently embedded in daily practices.

• “Wood and stone are still used, while traditional crafts have been partly replaced by commercial and mass-produced alternatives, with some renewed interest in reintroducing local artisanal practices.”

Figure 208 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 10

Figure 209 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 11

In the local context, the potential of traditional crafts to address current challenges is unevenly distributed, with stronger relevance in economic (30%) and cultural, political, social, and environmental dimensions (each 20%), while technical aspects remain more limited (10%). This suggests a broad but non-specialized contribution across multiple domains. At the same time, perceptions of traditional wood crafts show a polarized pattern, with responses concentrated at lower (66.7%) and higher levels (33.3%), indicating uneven recognition despite their cultural significance.

Figure 210 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 12

Figure 211 TIMBERHAUS Questionnaire for key stakeholders in Siena: responses to Question 13

In the local context, the use of traditional wood-related crafts shows no clear pattern, with responses evenly distributed between continued use, underuse, and uncertainty (each 33%), indicating a lack of consensus.

Responses to Questions 13-16 point to a weak and fragmented transmission of knowledge, with limited evidence of continuity across generations. References to traditional practices are scarce and non-specific (e.g. wood in construction, inlay), while responses to potential reintroduction are minimal and in some cases unrelated to traditional techniques. This suggests a context where traditional wood crafts are neither clearly preserved nor actively reinterpreted, with limited recognition of their potential in contemporary applications.

- “Woodworking is considered a traditional craft that should be passed on to future generations.”
- “Traditional techniques, such as joinery and wood processing, are only partially maintained, with some adaptation through modern methods.”

5. Comparative assessment and conclusions

What is unique and/or shared across the three contexts?

The comparative analysis of the three partner cities - Baia Mare, Berlin, and Siena - highlights significant differences, but also shared patterns, in terms of spatial structure, construction practices, material use, the relationship to local resources, cultural identity, and transformation processes across both urban and rural contexts.

Urban areas

In **urban areas**, the three cities present **distinct spatial configurations**. Baia Mare is characterized by a layered urban fabric resulting from the coexistence of a historic core, socialist planned expansions, and post-1990 developments, leading to fragmentation and strong interdependence with surrounding rural areas. This interdependence reflects the continued influence of rural resource systems and commuting patterns, although not fully supported by integrated planning. Berlin, in contrast, exhibits a dense metropolitan structure shaped by industrialization, war, division, and reunification, resulting in a multi-layered and partially fragmented urban system composed of historic urban areas, perimeter blocks, modernist housing estates, and redevelopment zones. Siena differs fundamentally, maintaining a compact medieval structure with a dense and irregular street network, strong spatial cohesion, and a high degree of morphological and architectural continuity ensured by heritage protection frameworks, with a clear relationship between topography, built form, and civic organization.

These differences are also reflected in **building typologies, techniques, materials**, and their relationship to local resources. In Baia Mare, there is a clear transition from traditional construction systems based on locally available materials toward prefabricated and standardized approaches introduced during the socialist period. Contemporary construction is dominated by brick and reinforced concrete, while timber-although historically rooted in regional practices-is used mainly in symbolic and aesthetic applications, particularly in cultural or touristic buildings. In Berlin, construction practices are largely defined by industrial systems, including masonry, concrete, steel, and prefabrication, reflecting a long-term shift away from locally sourced materials. Timber has historically played a secondary role, mainly in internal structural elements such as roofs and floors, but is increasingly reintroduced through engineered wood products, modular construction, and hybrid systems combining timber with steel and concrete, driven by sustainability objectives. In Siena, construction is dominated by stone and brick masonry, directly reflecting the availability of local geological resources such as travertine and limestone. Timber is consistently integrated within this system, used in internal structural elements, joinery, and reinforcement techniques such as tie rods and beams, contributing to structural stability rather than defining the architectural language.

Cultural and identity-related aspects further differentiate the three contexts, particularly in relation to how materials and construction techniques express local identity. In Baia Mare, urban identity is influenced by rural timber traditions and craftsmanship, although this connection is only partially reflected in contemporary construction practices, where traditional techniques are rarely applied beyond restoration or cultural initiatives. In Berlin, identity is shaped by a layered architectural timeline-from neoclassical and industrial to modernist and contemporary-rather than by specific materials, reflecting a shift from craftsmanship toward industrial and technological construction cultures. In Siena, cultural identity is strongly embedded in the continuity of materials, construction techniques, and urban form, where craftsmanship-particularly in masonry, woodwork, and detailing-remains closely tied to the historical fabric and civic traditions.

Over time, the three cities have followed **different transformation trajectories**. In Baia Mare, construction practices evolved from locally grounded, resource-based systems toward industrialized and standardized approaches during the socialist period, followed by post-socialist diversification, informal development, and increasing pressure on traditional timber heritage. In Berlin, the transformation reflects a longer trajectory from craft-based construction toward industrialized systems in the 19th and 20th centuries, reinforced by post-war reconstruction based on concrete and prefabrication, and more recently complemented by a renewed interest in timber as part of climate-oriented construction strategies. In Siena, transformation has been characterized by continuity, with changes occurring primarily through controlled adaptation, where traditional materials and construction logics are maintained while integrating contemporary requirements.

Rural areas

In **rural areas**, all three contexts reveal a strong **relationship between settlement structures, natural landscapes, and local resource availability**, although expressed differently. In Baia Mare, rural areas are structured by ethnographic regions and characterized by diverse settlement patterns adapted to valleys, hillsides, and local circulation routes. The built environment reflects a close integration with the landscape and a direct reliance on locally available materials, particularly timber. In Brandenburg, the rural context is shaped by a forest-rich landscape, where woodland availability has historically influenced settlement distribution, construction techniques, and economic activities, linking forestry directly to both building practices and regional development. In the Siena region, rural settlements are organized in relation to a hilly agricultural landscape, where land use, topography, and local material resources—such as stone, clay, and timber—define both spatial organization and construction practices.

Building practices and material use in rural areas show clearer contrasts, particularly in relation to timber and construction techniques. In Baia Mare, timber represents the primary structural material and forms the basis of a comprehensive vernacular construction system, including houses, annexes, gates, and churches. This system is supported by specific techniques such as Blockbau, log and beam construction, and traditional joinery methods (e.g. dovetail joints, cheotoare, wooden pegs), relying almost exclusively on locally sourced wood species such as oak, fir, and spruce. In Brandenburg, timber has also played a historically central role, both as a construction material and as an economic resource, with techniques such as Blockbau, Schrotholzbau, and Fachwerk systems, where timber frames are combined with clay or brick infill. These practices are closely linked to forestry and material processing knowledge, although their role has evolved over time with industrialization and more recent technological innovation, including prefabrication and engineered wood systems. In contrast, in the Siena region, construction is primarily based on stone and brick masonry, reflecting geological conditions and local resource distribution, while timber plays a complementary role in structural elements, interiors, and artisanal production, using locally available species such as chestnut and olive wood.

Cultural identity in rural areas is strongly tied to material use, craftsmanship, and local resource systems across all three contexts. In Baia Mare, timber architecture and woodworking traditions form a core component of regional identity, expressed through elements such as wooden churches, carved gates, and decorated houses, as well as through a wide range of crafts including woodworking, carving, textiles, pottery, and metalwork. In Brandenburg, timber construction reflects a resource-based identity linked to forests, where craftsmanship is rooted in manual processing techniques and the multifunctional use of wood in construction, tools, and economic activities. In Siena, identity is expressed through the coherence between landscape, materials, and built form, with crafts linked to locally available resources such as stone, wood, ceramics, and textiles, although timber does not play a dominant structural role.

The transformation processes in rural areas also reveal both shared and divergent trends. In Baia Mare, post-1990 changes have led to depopulation, reduced maintenance of traditional buildings, changes in land ownership and forestry use, and the increasing replacement of vernacular architecture with modern constructions lacking local identity, alongside selective preservation driven by tourism. In Brandenburg, timber construction declined with industrialization and the introduction of new materials such as steel and concrete, but has recently re-emerged through sustainability-driven innovation, resulting in a coexistence of heritage preservation and advanced timber technologies. In the Siena region, rural areas show strong continuity in material traditions, with gradual adaptation to contemporary needs and increasing integration of sustainable practices, including timber, alongside dominant stone-based construction systems.

Overall, the comparison highlights three distinct trajectories in relation to timber, materials, and construction practices: a context of strong vernacular timber continuity under pressure and partially disconnected from contemporary construction (Baia Mare), a context of industrial transformation with a renewed technological and policy-driven interest in timber (Berlin–Brandenburg), and a context of material continuity rooted in stone-based construction, where timber plays a complementary but persistent role (Siena). These differences are essential for understanding how local resources, construction techniques, and cultural identity shape the current and future potential of timber in each context.

Comparison between the soft-desk research and the stakeholder responses

The comparison between the soft desk research and the stakeholder responses reveals a generally high level of alignment across the three partner cities, while also highlighting important differences in how construction practices, timber use, and traditional knowledge are structurally embedded versus how they are perceived and operationalized in practice. In addition, stakeholder input provides a clearer understanding of the concrete challenges and opportunities shaping the adoption of timber in each context.

In **Baia Mare**, both the desk research and stakeholder responses confirm the dominance of conventional construction systems in urban areas, particularly the widespread use of concrete and brick and the limited structural role of timber. While the desk research identifies timber as primarily symbolic or aesthetic in urban contexts, stakeholders report a broader application of wood, especially in renovation projects where it is used structurally, indicating a difference between systemic patterns and project-level practices. In rural areas, both sources highlight the central role of timber and traditional craftsmanship; however, while the desk research emphasizes the decline of these practices and their replacement with modern construction lacking local identity, stakeholders indicate that traditional techniques are still present to a moderate extent, suggesting a slower perceived rate of loss.

Stakeholder responses also provide a more detailed account of the barriers affecting timber use in Baia Mare. These include the strong dominance of conventional materials, regulatory constraints—particularly related to fire safety and approval processes—limited technical capacity, and a shortage of skilled workforce. Additional constraints such as low levels of prefabrication, weak investor confidence, and concerns related to durability and performance further limit adoption. At the same time, stakeholders identify significant opportunities that complement the desk research findings, including the high potential of timber in renovation and heritage-related projects, the growing importance of energy efficiency and NZEB requirements, and the availability of local timber resources. The potential to develop prefabricated timber systems and to integrate traditional construction techniques into contemporary architecture further reinforces the role of wood as both a cultural and construction resource.

In the **Berlin–Brandenburg** context, the desk research and stakeholder responses are largely aligned in identifying timber as historically secondary in urban construction, with a growing role in contemporary sustainable building practices. However, a difference emerges in the level of maturity of this transition. While the desk research emphasizes the recent re-emergence of timber driven by regulatory change and sustainability goals, stakeholders suggest that timber is already being used alongside conventional materials in current projects, particularly in structural applications, indicating a more advanced stage of practical integration. At the same time, stakeholders assess the sustainability level of current construction practices as relatively low, pointing to a gap between strategic ambitions and perceived implementation on the ground.

The stakeholder responses also highlight a set of structural challenges that are less explicitly addressed in the desk research. These include high costs and limited economic competitiveness of timber compared to concrete and steel, regulatory complexity, limited technical expertise, and the persistence of established construction practices that slow down innovation. Timber construction remains largely confined to pilot projects and has not yet been scaled systemically. In rural areas, additional barriers include lack of skilled labor, limited access to training, and reduced trust in timber as a durable material. At the same time, stakeholders identify strong opportunities for development, including the potential to scale timber construction through prefabricated and modular systems, supported by policy frameworks, financial incentives, and CO₂-related instruments. The integration of timber into life-cycle assessment frameworks, the role of the public sector in promoting circular construction, and the potential of renovation and transformation of existing building stock are also seen as key drivers for future expansion.

In **Siena**, the comparison between desk research and stakeholder perceptions shows a high level of consistency in terms of material dominance, construction practices, and the strong role of heritage. Both sources confirm that construction is largely based on brick and stone, with timber playing a secondary role, mainly in structural elements, interiors, and renovation works. However, stakeholders place a stronger emphasis on renovation as the dominant type of intervention, with very limited new construction, while the desk research presents a broader overview of the built environment without prioritizing this dynamic. In rural areas, both sources highlight the strong relationship between landscape, materials, and cultural identity, although stakeholders emphasize more clearly the gradual decline in the everyday use of traditional crafts and their limited reintroduction in contemporary construction.

Stakeholder responses further detail the constraints affecting timber use in Siena, including the strong dominance of conventional materials, strict regulatory frameworks in historic and UNESCO-protected areas, and technical and cultural barriers that influence material choices. Timber is often perceived as context-specific and less suitable for structural or façade applications, while weak supply chains, high costs, and maintenance concerns reduce its competitiveness. Limited innovation and reliance on traditional construction practices also contribute to the slow adoption of timber solutions. At the same time, stakeholders identify a range of opportunities that align with, but also extend beyond, the desk research findings. These include the strong potential for timber use in renovation projects, increasing demand for energy efficiency, and the role of public projects and small-scale interventions as entry points for timber applications. Additional opportunities lie in combining traditional materials with modern techniques, adapting timber use to heritage-sensitive contexts, and strengthening skills development, supply chains, and policy support to enable a gradual and context-compatible integration of wood in construction.

Across all three contexts, a consistent pattern emerges in the relationship between desk-based analysis and stakeholder perception. While the desk research captures long-term structural trends, including the decline of traditional practices, the dominance of industrialized construction systems, and the evolving role of timber, stakeholder responses provide a more detailed and practice-oriented perspective. They highlight the concrete barriers—such as regulatory constraints, economic pressures, technical capacity, and workforce limitations—that directly influence implementation, as well as the specific opportunities through which timber can be more effectively integrated into

contemporary construction. Overall, the two perspectives are complementary: the desk research outlines the systemic conditions and trajectories, while stakeholder input clarifies the operational realities, revealing both the constraints and the pathways for expanding the role of timber across different urban and rural contexts.

5.1. Comparative assessment between Partner Cities. Soft-desk research

BAIA MARE, ROMANIA		BERLIN, GERMANY		SIENA, ITALY	
Urban area	Rural area	Urban area	Rural area	Urban area	Rural area
<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layered urban fabric: historic core, socialist planned expansions, post-1990 developments Historic center: compact plots, street alignment, mixed-use heritage typologies Socialist era introduced prefabricated housing estates and industrial platforms, shifting to standardized systems Post-1990: urban sprawl, informal construction, and functional fragmentation Strong urban-rural interdependence, Baia Mare as a regional hub <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typologies: historic perimeter blocks, courtyard houses, individual housing, socialist housing estates, mixed-use corridors, industrial/logistic areas Dominance of brick and reinforced concrete Transition from traditional construction to prefabricated and standardized systems Timber used mainly in symbolic/aesthetic roles (cultural, touristic buildings) <p>Cultural & symbolic/identity elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban identity influenced by regional timber traditions and rural heritage 	<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predominantly rural territory: low density, dispersed settlements, agro-forestry landscape Settlement patterns: linear along valleys, dispersed on hillsides, compact clusters, isolated settlements Strong integration of built environment with landscape and topography Households organized as agropastoral units with dwelling and annexes <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timber is the primary structural material (oak, fir, spruce) Use of Blockbau systems, log/beam structures, traditional joinery (dovetail, cheotoare, wooden pegs) Use of earth (infill), stone (foundations), shingles/thatch/tile roofs Construction based on local materials: wood, earth, stone Timber used across scales: houses, annexes, gates, churches, objects Architecture adapted to climate, terrain, and agricultural use <p>Cultural & symbolic/identity elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structured by four ethnographic regions with distinct identities Timber architecture as core regional identity 	<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dense metropolitan structure shaped by industrialization, war, division, and reunification Combination of historic core, perimeter blocks (Blockrand), modernist estates, redevelopment areas Functional zoning leading to uneven development and fragmentation (East/West) Transition toward densification, infill, and expansion into peri-urban areas Hybrid structure combining compact core and dispersed metropolitan growth <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typologies: Gründerzeit perimeter blocks, modernist housing estates (Siedlungen), Plattenbau estates, contemporary multi-story housing, industrial areas Dominance of masonry, concrete, steel, prefabrication systems Timber historically secondary, used mainly in internal structures (roofs, floors) Contemporary use of engineered timber, modular and hybrid systems (timber-steel-concrete) <p>Cultural & symbolic / identity elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identity expressed through a layered architectural timeline 	<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest-rich landscape (over one-third woodland) shaping settlements and land use Settlement types: linear street villages (Straßendorf), Angerdorf, clustered villages (Haufendorf), dispersed farmsteads Strong relationship between settlement patterns, forestry, agriculture, and transport routes <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typologies: farmsteads, Fachwerk houses, timber-framed barns (Fachwerkscheunen), auxiliary agricultural buildings Timber historically primary construction material (especially pine) Techniques: Blockbau, Schrotholzbau, Fachwerk (timber frame with clay/brick infill) Timber used for structures, tools, furniture, infrastructure, and energy production <p>Cultural & symbolic / identity elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timber construction reflects resource-based rural identity linked to forests Strong link between woodland availability and vernacular building culture Craftsmanship based on local knowledge, manual processing, and forestry practices 	<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compact medieval urban structure, dense, irregular street network, strong spatial cohesion Strong morphological and architectural continuity due to heritage protection Urban form closely linked to topography, civic organization, and built structure Limited and controlled urban expansion beyond the historic core <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typologies: palazzi, religious buildings, attached medieval fabric, modern residential areas Construction dominated by stone and brick masonry Timber used internally (roofs, floors) and externally (windows, doors) Timber also used in reinforcement systems (tie rods, beams), for structural stability Use of travertine for façade elements and architectural detailing <p>Cultural & symbolic/identity elements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identity rooted in medieval urban form, contrade system, and civic traditions Strong role of craftsmanship (masonry, woodwork, metalwork, ceramics) Timber present in interior decorative, and artisanal applications 	<p>Spatial form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hilly landscape with settlements shaped by ridgelines, valleys, and agricultural land Settlement types: hilltop compact villages, dispersed farmsteads, clustered hamlets (borghi), linear settlements along roads, agricultural estate complexes (podere) Strong integration between settlements and productive landscapes (vineyards, olive groves, fields) <p>Building typologies, techniques & materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typologies: farmhouses, rural estates (podere), annexes, agricultural complexes Buildings composed of main dwellings + functional annexes (storage, production, housing) Construction dominated by stone and brick, reflecting geological diversity Use of local materials: travertine, limestone (e.g., pietra alberese), clay Timber used in structures and interiors (floors, ceilings, furniture) Local wood species (e.g., chestnut, olive wood) are used in both construction and artisanal production. <p>Cultural & symbolic/identity elements</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Craftsmanship present mainly in heritage, restoration, and cultural initiatives <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shift from local/traditional to industrialized construction systems (socialist period). • Post-socialist diversification introduces external architectural influences • Growing tension between urban development and timber heritage preservation • Growing interest in heritage valorization and adaptive reuse, though still limited in scale. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key elements: wooden churches (UNESCO), carved gates, traditional houses • Wooden churches represent peak technical and symbolic expression • Rich ornamental motifs (religious, geometric, symbolic) • Strong presence of woodworking, carving, textiles, pottery, metalwork, agriculture-based crafts • Crafts embedded in self-sufficient rural economy and cultural continuity <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-1990: depopulation, reduced maintenance, and changes in land ownership and forestry use • Increasing replacement of traditional buildings with modern constructions lacking local identity • Migration introduces external styles and hybrid architecture • Tourism supports selective preservation and reinterpretation • Tension between heritage loss and revival of timber traditions 	<p>(neoclassical, modernist, socialist, contemporary)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timber not central to historic urban identity, unlike rural contexts • Increasing symbolic role of timber as marker of sustainability and ecological awareness • Shift from craftsmanship to industrial and technological construction culture <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition from craft-based construction to industrialized systems (19th–20th century) • Post-war reconstruction dominated by concrete and prefabrication • Post-2000: timber re-emerges through regulation, innovation, and climate policies • Increasing role of timber in sustainable and climate-neutral urban development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timber central to economic systems (rafts, tools, glass production, etc.) <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decline of timber with industrialization and new materials (steel, concrete) • 20th century: timber becomes secondary in mainstream construction • Recent revival through sustainable construction, innovation, and engineered wood • Coexistence of heritage preservation and modern timber technologies • Timber repositioned as key material for ecological transition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architecture reflects continuity between material use, culture, and social practices <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High continuity due to strong heritage protection frameworks • Integration of modern interventions respecting historic fabric • Continued use of traditional materials alongside contemporary needs • Evolution through adaptation rather than disruption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong link between materials, landscape, and cultural identity • Crafts based on local resources (wood, stone, ceramics, textiles) • Woodcraft (e.g., olive wood) reflects resource-efficient and place-based traditions • Rural identity expressed through coherence of architecture and landscape <p>Transformations over time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong continuity of material traditions (stone, brick), with gradual adaptation to modern needs. • Increasing integration of sustainable practices, including timber in contemporary construction and renovation. • Projects combining traditional materials with modern design reflect a reinterpretation of local identity. • Emergence of a circular approach to wood use, including reuse, restoration, and sustainable forestry. • Current dynamic: balance between preservation and innovation, with timber playing a complementary but growing role.
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5.2. Comparative assessment between Partner Cities. Stakeholder responses

BAIA MARE, ROMANIA		BERLIN, GERMANY		SIENA, ITALY	
Urban area	Rural area	Urban area	Rural area	Urban area	Rural area
<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: Mixed development of new construction and renovation; • Most common techniques: on-site methods with limited prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials are concrete and brick, followed by wood; • New projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick, followed by wood, concrete, and stone; • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - medium; • Renovation projects: Main structural material is wood, followed by concrete and stone • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick followed by stone • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - generally perceived as slightly more sustainable than new construction; • Recent changes: Increased focus on energy efficiency; • Traditional architectural elements present: moderate; 	<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: new constructions; • Most common techniques: on-site methods with limited prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials are wood followed by stone and concrete • New projects: exterior materials are dominated by wood and brick; • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - medium; • Renovation projects: Main structural material is wood, followed by concrete • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick followed by stone • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - medium; • Recent changes: Increased focus on energy efficiency in recent practices; followed by the return to traditional materials, techniques, styles • Traditional architectural elements present: moderate; 	<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: new construction • Most common techniques: shows uncertainty and limited use of prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials are concrete, wood, and brick, • New projects: Exterior materials are dominated by wood • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - low; • Renovation projects: Main structural material is wood, followed by concrete • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by wood, followed by concrete • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - medium • Recent changes: Increase in density • Traditional architectural elements present: high 	<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: Mixed development of new construction and renovation; • Most common techniques: on-site methods and limited prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials are brick and concrete • New projects: Exterior materials are dominated by wood, followed by stone and brick • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - low • Renovation projects: Main structural material is wood, followed stone • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by wood followed by glass • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - generally perceived as low and medium • Recent changes: Increased focus on energy efficiency; • Traditional architectural elements present: moderate; 	<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: renovation, with very limited new construction; • Most common techniques: on-site methods with limited prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials is brick, followed by wood; • New projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick followed by concrete; • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - medium; • Renovation projects: Main structural material is wood, followed by concrete • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick followed by stone • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - medium; • Recent changes: Increased focus on energy efficiency; • Traditional architectural elements present: high; 	<p>CONSTRUCTION & DESIGN Local Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most commonly implemented projects: renovation very limited new construction; • Most common techniques: on-site methods with limited prefabrication; • New projects: main structural materials is brick, followed by concrete; • New projects: Exterior materials are dominated by brick, followed by stone; • Level of sustainability of the current construction practices - medium; • Renovation projects: Main structural material is steel, followed by wood • Renovation projects: Exterior materials are dominated by wood followed by stone • Level of sustainability of the current renovation practices - medium; • Recent changes: Increased focus on energy efficiency; • Traditional architectural elements present: high;
<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood is generally perceived very positive in interior finishes & furniture in new and renovation buildings & positively in exterior finishes and structure of new buildings; • Main barriers: technical • Constraints: technical, regulatory, and cost barriers, along with 	<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood is positively perceived across most applications, especially interior finished of new and renovated buildings; • Main barriers: economic and social • Constraints: economic constraints, lack of skilled labor, limited trust; external factors (e.g urban 	<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood is generally perceived positively, especially in structure of new buildings; • Main barriers are regulatory and technical, • Constraints: Regulatory complexity, Fire safety approvals, high costs, technical knowledge • Opportunities: policy support, economic instruments, scaling mechanisms, Co2 pricing, 	<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood is positively perceived, especially in structure of renovated buildings and exterior finished of new buildings; • Main barriers are economic and technical • Constraints: cost pressures, regulatory frameworks, persistence of established construction 	<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood is generally very positive perceived in interior finishes and positively perceived across all the context, with more focus on structure of new and renovated buildings and interior finishes of new buildings; • Main barriers are technical and 	<p>Wood Use in Local Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wood is generally very positive perceived in interior finishes or furniture in renovated buildings and positively perceived across all the context, with more focus on structure of new buildings; • Main barriers are technical • Constraints: regulatory

<p>concerns about durability and performance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities: local resources availability, prefabrication (NZEB), growing interest in wood-based solutions, renovation, public space projects, and integrating traditional craftsmanship <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic urban fabric periods: layered development from medieval to modern periods • Historic urban fabric styles: Baroque, Classical, Neoclassical, Gothic, and Art Nouveau • Structural materials in historic buildings: wood and stone • External materials in historic buildings: brick and stone • Heritage / historic buildings and architectural features preserved medium extent • Heritage buildings valued and connected with identity and pride: medium and very large extent • Historic construction materials, techniques/ styles less used now: traditional materials and techniques declining • Historic construction materials, techniques or styles reintroduced in modern construction: limited reintroduction mainly through restoration and context-specific interventions 	<p>construction models and environmental concerns)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities: local resources, skills development, cultural identity, incl. The need to improve workforce qualification and tradition-based construction practices; affordability, sustainability and sectoral opportunities such as tourism <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic urban fabric periods: layered development, primarily from the 17th-19th centuries, with earlier references. • Historic urban fabric styles: vernacular Maramureş style, Gothic and Baroque elements. • Structural materials in historic buildings: wood and stone • External materials in historic buildings: stone • Heritage / historic buildings and architectural features preserved medium extent • Heritage buildings valued and connected with identity and pride: large and very large extent • Historic construction materials, techniques/ styles less used now: traditional materials and techniques declining • Historic construction materials, techniques or styles reintroduced in modern construction: limited reintroduction mainly through restoration and context-specific interventions • Techniques include traditional wood joinery, wooden shingles, and mixed systems; • Characteristic elements include porches, carved wood, and steep roofs; • Traditional practices are being replaced by concrete and prefabricated systems; 	<p>prefabricated construction, improved LCA</p> <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <p><i>*All respondents are affiliated with the Construction and Design sector</i></p>	<p>practices, performance and durability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities: financial support, improved access to knowledge and training, and the development of prefabricated solutions <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <p><i>*All respondents are affiliated with the Construction and Design sector</i></p>	<p>cultural;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constraints include weak supply chains, high costs, and maintenance concerns, durability • Opportunities: skills development, improved supply and distribution, public projects & small scale interventions and new projects. <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic urban fabric periods: medieval with consistent references to the middle ages • Historic urban fabric styles: homogeneous structure, traditional masonry, strong historical continuity • Structural materials in historic buildings: brick and stone • External materials in historic buildings: brick and stone • Heritage / historic buildings and architectural features preserved medium and very large extent • Heritage buildings valued and connected with identity and pride: very large extent • Historic construction materials, techniques/ styles less used now: traditional materials and techniques declining • Historic construction materials, techniques or styles reintroduced in modern construction: limited and non systemic 	<p>restrictions, cultural inertia, technical capacity, strong planning constraints in rural areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities: skills development, improved supply and distribution, public projects & small scale interventions and new projects. <p>HERITAGE & CRAFTSMANSHIP Local Historic Construction Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic urban fabric periods: medieval and renaissance • Historic urban fabric styles: vernacular rural typology based on traditional farmhouses, rooted in medieval layouts and later adapted through subsequent interventions • Structural materials in historic buildings: brick and stone • External materials in historic buildings: stone followed by brick • Heritage / historic buildings and architectural features preserved medium extent • Heritage buildings valued and connected with identity and pride: very large extent • Historic construction materials, techniques/ styles less used now: traditional materials and techniques declining • Historic construction materials, techniques or styles reintroduced in modern construction: evolution of traditional practices is limited, with weak reintroduction dynamics;
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Local Historic Crafts	Local Historic Crafts	Local Historic Crafts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional crafts are based on materials such as wood, stone, metal, textiles, and ceramics; • Main crafts include woodworking, stone masonry, metalwork, pottery, and textile production; • Crafts play a multifunctional role in the economy, cultural heritage, tourism, and education; • Challenge: there is a visible decline in everyday use due to industrial production and mass-produced alternatives; • Challenges that could be addressed by preserving or reintroducing the practice of traditional crafts: political • Traditional crafts remain strongly associated with local identity and cultural value; • Continuity is uneven, with practices preserved in some contexts but gradually diminishing overall; • Reintroduction occurs mainly through cultural projects, workshops, and heritage initiatives; • Current use is mostly symbolic or tourism-related rather than functional; • Traditional wood crafts are still in use in the city/region and remain strongly associated with local identity and cultural value; 	<p><i>*All respondents are affiliated with the Construction and Design sector</i></p>	<p>Traditional crafts: carpentry, stone masonry, metalwork, ceramics, and textiles - without a clearly dominant specialization;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuity of practice is high; • Crafts are mainly linked to preservation of cultural heritage today; • Main challenges in maintaining the practice include industrial competition, lack of craftsmen, and reduced cultural relevance • Challenges that could be addressed by preserving or reintroducing the practice of traditional crafts: economic • There is a clear decline in everyday use, with replacement by mass-produced alternatives; • Reintroduction is selective and limited, mainly symbolic rather than functional; • Perception of value is uneven, with polarized responses ; • Transmission of knowledge is weak, with limited generational continuity; <p>Traditional wood crafts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered valuable and associated with a sense of identity to a small extent • Neither clearly preserved nor actively reinterpreted • Partially maintained, with limited adaptation to contemporary uses;

ANNEXES

TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

30.04.2026, 10:11

TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

TIMBERHAUS aims to accelerate the green and circular transition of construction by strengthening links between the forest and construction sectors, developing value chains for underused wood types and species, and overcoming barriers to scaling up wood-based building in Europe.

The project also focuses on **embedding the New European Bauhaus core values - sustainable, beautiful, together** - into urban and strategic contexts by focusing on **citizen values, local culture and traditions**.

This questionnaire aims to **collect perceptions on local historical and cultural traditions of crafts and design languages in urban and rural areas and wood use**, with a particular focus on how these are understood, valued, and applied by local stakeholders within each of the 3 Partner cities: Berlin (Germany), Baia Mare (Romania), and Siena (Italy).

The findings of this questionnaire will:

- Inform future local stakeholder engagement activities aimed at co-creating solutions for the climate-smart use of wood in the 3 contexts: Berlin, Baia Mare and Siena;
- Integrate insights into wood building blueprints and digital pilots;
- Ground decarbonisation strategies and city plans in local cultural identities;
- Identify heritage-based practices that can inspire innovative construction and policy agendas.

The questionnaire will take approximately 15–20 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance for your time!

For any questions or clarifications, please get in touch with the project partners responsible for stakeholder participation:

- Mădălina Rusen, Urbasofia (madalina.rusen@urbasofia.eu)
- Ellen Gale, Climate KIC (Ellen.Gale@climate-kic.org)

You may also read more about the project and its goals on <https://timberhaus.eu/>

* *Indică o întrebare obligatorie*

TIMBERHAUS Partner Cities

Privacy Statement

This Data Protection Notice (DPN) informs you about the collection and processing of personal data in the context of the **TIMBERHAUS EU project**, specifically regarding the **stakeholder questionnaire aimed at understanding local perceptions**. Your data will be processed in accordance with **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)**.

1. Purpose of the Data Collection.

The purpose of this data collection is to gain insights into stakeholder perceptions at the local level as part of the TIMBERHAUS project's research activities. The purpose of this data collection is to gain insights into stakeholder perceptions at the local /regional level as part of the TIMBERHAUS project's research activities. Your responses will help us understand cultural traditions, crafts and design languages, and local/regional construction practices in both urban and rural contexts.

2. What Data is Collected.

The following data will be collected:

- Name of your organisation
- City and/or region of affiliation
- Responses to the questionnaire
- Email address (only if you choose to share it, for the purpose of project communication such as follow-up, invitations to workshops, or subscription to the project newsletter)

3. Legal Basis for Processing. The legal basis for processing your data is

- Article 6(1)(e) GDPR: Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest, namely scientific research.
- Voluntary participation: You provide data by freely completing the questionnaire. The provision of your email address is optional and will only be used for project-related communication.

4. Who Will Access Your Data Data will only be accessed by:

- The TIMBERHAUS project consortium partners
- Designated researchers or data analysts working on the project
- Authorized personnel responsible for managing and evaluating the questionnaire results
- Aggregated and anonymised results included in project reports or publications. No individual responses will be published or shared

5. Data Storage and Protection.

Your data will be stored on secure servers used by the project partners, with appropriate technical and organisational safeguards in place to protect against unauthorised access, disclosure, or alteration.

1. *By filing out this questionnaire, I agree that TIMBERHAUS can collect and use the information I provide for qualitative and quantitative research purposes, analysis and reporting within the scope of the TIMBERHAUS project.* *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Yes, i agree
- No, i do not agree

General information

2. 1. In which partner city are you based? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Berlin, Germany
- Siena, Italy
- Baia Mare, Romania

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

3. 2. Which of the following stakeholder groups do you belong to ? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Heritage and Crafts – craftsmen, artisans, heritage experts, cultural institutions, craft schools *Treci la întrebarea 47*
- Construction and Design – architects, engineers, builders, urban planner, professional associations
Treci la întrebarea 9

4. 3. What is the name of the organisation / company do you represent ? *

5. 4. Which discipline do you work within? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Architecture
- Construction
- Engineering
- Renovation or restoration
- Woodworking or carpentry
- Product/furniture design/manufacture using wood
- Planning
- Altele:

6. 5. Do you collaborate with any local/regional/national clusters or associations in the wood value chain ? *

Your answers will help us identify other potential relevant stakeholders for the topic of the project

Marchează un singur oval.

- Yes
- No

7. 6. If yes, please mention below *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

8. 7. Where are the projects you are involved with typically located ? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Urban area (within city boundaries)
- Rural area (outside city boundaries) Example: a small village close to Baia Mare which is mostly considered a rural area
- Both urban and rural areas
- Altele:
—

Local Urban Construction Practices

*This section aims to capture perceptions of what defines local construction practices in **urban** areas in your region. It explores the most common materials, techniques, and architectural/design styles used in **urban** areas today, as well as their level of sustainability and the presence of traditional or distinctive elements.*

9. 1. What types of **construction projects** are most common within the local **urban** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- New build
- Refurbishment
- Not sure
- Altele:
—

10. 2. What types of **construction technique/approach** are most common within the local urban area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- On-site works
- Limited use of prefabricated components
- Extensive use of prefabricated components
- Not sure
- Altele:
—

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

11. 3. What are the most common **structural materials** for new build construction projects within the local **urban** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Brick
- Timber
- Stone
- Steel
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

12. 4. What are the most common **external materials** for new build construction projects in the local **urban** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Brick
- Timber
- Stone
- Steel
- Glass
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

13. 5. In your opinion, how sustainable are the current **new build construction** practices in the local **urban** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Sustainable

14. 6. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible. *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

15. 7. What are the most common **structural materials for refurbishment** projects within the local **urban** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Steel
- Timber
- Stone
- Brick
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

16. 8. What are the most common **external materials for refurbishment** projects within the local **urban** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
- Stone
- Glass
- Metal
- Timber
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

17. 9. In your opinion, how sustainable are the current **refurbishment practices** in the local **urban** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not Sustainable

18. 10. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

19. 11. Have you noticed any **recent changes** in the way buildings are constructed or renovated within your local **urban area**? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Increased focus on energy efficiency
- Increased focus on sustainable materials
- Increased use of prefabrication
- Increased density
- Decreased density
- Change in typologies
- Return to traditional materials, techniques and styles
- No
- Not sure

20. 12. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **urban area** which have been recently reintroduced into modern construction? *

21. 13. To what extent are **traditional architectural elements present in buildings or urban spaces** in your city? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not Very common

22. 14. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible. *

23. 15. Are there any **building practices** (e.g techniques, architectural and design styles/elements or approaches) in your city that you consider **distinctive or unique** ? *

If yes, please specify them and explain why you consider them distinctive or unique

Wood Use in Local Urban construction

The following questions explore the use of wood in construction within **urban** areas. They examine how timber use is perceived across different contexts, what barriers exist to its wider use and what opportunities there are for its increased prevalence.

24. 1. How do you perceive the **use of wood for the following contexts** in your **urban** area ? *

Marchează un singur oval pentru fiecare rând.

	Very negatively	Negatively	Neutrally	Positively	Very positively
Structure of new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
External finishes of new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal finishes or furniture within new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Structure of refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
External finishes in refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal finishes or furniture in refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Public realm interventions (e.g. benches, bus shelters, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

25. 2. Which of the following types of **barriers** do you think affect the use of wood in construction in your **urban** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Economic (e.g. high material costs)
- Technical (e.g. limited knowledge of timber construction, lack of skilled workforce)
- Legislative / Regulatory (e.g. restrictive or prohibitive building codes or standards)
- Political (e.g. lack of support from local authority)
- Cultural (e.g. aesthetic expectations, traditional building practices)
- Social (e.g. public perceptions towards timber)
- Environmental (e.g. material sourcing, forestry practices)
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

26. 3. Please elaborate / provide additional specific information about the barriers which you think are most critical, where * possible.

27. 4. Do you see **opportunities** for expanding the use of wood in construction in your **urban** area? If yes, which ones? *

Local Rural Construction Practices

*This section aims to capture perceptions of what defines local construction practices in **rural** areas in your region. It explores the most common materials, techniques, and architectural/design styles used in **rural** areas today, as well as their level of sustainability and the presence of traditional or distinctive elements.*

28. 1. What types of **construction projects** are most common within the local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- New build
- Refurbishment
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

29. 2. What types of **construction technique/approach** are most common within the local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- On-site works
- Limited use of prefabricated components
- Extensive use of prefabricated components
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

30. 3. What are the most common **structural materials** for new build construction projects within the local **rural** area? *

Please select the top three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Brick
- Timber
- Stone
- Steel
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

31. 4. What are the most common **external materials** for new build construction projects in the local **rural** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Brick
- Timber
- Stone
- Steel
- Glass
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

32. 5. In your opinion, how sustainable are the current **new build construction** practices in the local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not Sustainable

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

33. 6. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible. *

34. 7. What are the most common **structural materials for refurbishment** projects within the local **rural** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Concrete
- Steel
- Timber
- Stone
- Brick
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

35. 8. What are the most common **external materials for refurbishment** projects within the local **rural** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
- Stone
- Glass
- Metal
- Timber
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

36. 9. In your opinion, how sustainable are the current **refurbishment practices** in the local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Sustainable

37. 10. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

38. 11. Have you noticed any **recent changes** in the way buildings are constructed or refurbished within your local **rural** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Increased focus on energy efficiency
- Increased focus on sustainable materials
- Increased use of prefabrication
- Increased density
- Decreased density
- Change in typologies
- Return to traditional materials, techniques and styles
- No
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

39. 12. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **rural** area which have been recently reintroduced into modern construction? *

40. 13. To what extent are **traditional architectural elements present in buildings or public spaces** in rural area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not Very common

41. 14. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible. *

42. 15. Are there any **building practices** (e.g techniques, architectural and design styles/elements or approaches) in rural area that you consider **distinctive or unique** ? *

If yes, please specify them and explain why you consider them distinctive or unique

Wood Use in Local Rural construction

The following questions explore the use of wood in construction within **rural** areas. They examine how timber use is perceived across different contexts, what barriers exist to its wider use and what opportunities there are for its increased prevalence.

43. 1. How do you perceive the **use of wood for the following contexts** in rural area/your city? *

Marchează un singur oval pentru fiecare rând.

	Very negatively	Negatively	Neutrally	Positively	Very positively
Structure of new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
External finishes of new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal finishes or furniture within new buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Structure of refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
External finishes in refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal finishes or furniture in refurbished buildings	<input type="radio"/>				
Public realm interventions (e.g. benches, bus shelters, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

44. 2. Which of the following types of barriers do you think affect the use of wood in construction in your **rural** area? *

Please select up to three that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Economic (e.g. high material costs)
- Technical (e.g. limited knowledge of timber construction, lack of skilled workforce)
- Legislative / Regulatory (e.g. restrictive or prohibitive building codes or standards)
- Political (e.g. lack of support from local authority)
- Cultural (e.g. aesthetic expectations, traditional building practices)
- Social (e.g. public perceptions towards timber)
- Environmental (e.g. material sourcing, forestry practices)
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

45. 3. Please elaborate / provide additional specific information about the barriers which you think are most critical where * possible

46. 4. Do you see **opportunities** for expanding the use of wood in construction in your **rural** area? If yes, which ones? *

Treci la întrebarea 80

Local Urban Historic Construction Practices

*This section aims to collect information around historic construction practices within **urban** areas in your region. It explores the most common materials and techniques used as well as their unique or distinctive attributes and to what extent historic buildings have been retained, protected and valued by the local community.*

47. 1. In which period(s) was majority of the **historic urban fabric** within the local **urban** area constructed? *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

48. 2. In which style(s) was majority of the **historic urban fabric** within the local **urban** area constructed ? *

49. 3. What were the most common **structural materials** used in the construction of historic buildings within the local **urban** area ? *

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
 Stone
 Timber
 Not sure
 Altele: _____

50. 4. What were the most common **external materials** used in the construction of historic buildings within the local **urban** area? *

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
 Stone
 Timber
 Not sure
 Altele: _____

51. 5. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **urban** area which you consider **distinctive or unique** ? *

52. 6. To what extent have **heritage / historic buildings and architectural features** been retained within your local **urban** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not To a very large extent

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

53. 7. In your opinion, to what extent are **heritage buildings** seen as valuable and attributed a sense of identity and pride *
within the local **urban** area?

Marchează un singur oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not To a very large extent

54. 8. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **urban** area which are now less used *
due to modern alternatives or industrialisation?

55. 9. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **urban** area which have been *
recently reintroduced into modern construction?

Local Rural Historic Construction Practices

*This section
aims to collate information around historic construction practices within **rural**
areas in your region. It explores the most common materials and techniques used
as well as their unique or distinctive attributes and to what extent historic
buildings have been retained, protected and valued by the local community.*

56. 1. In which period(s) was majority of the **historic rural fabric** within the local **urban** area constructed? *

57. 2. In which style(s) was majority of the **historic rural fabric** within the local **urban** area constructed? *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

58. 3. What were the most common **structural materials** used in the construction of historic buildings within the local **rural** area? *

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
 Stone
 Timber
 Not sure
 Altele: _____

59. 4. What were the most common **external materials** used in the construction of historic buildings within the local **rural** area? *

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Brick
 Stone
 Timber
 Not sure
 Altele: _____

60. 5. To what extent have **heritage / historic buildings and architectural features** been retained within your local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not To a very large extent

61. 6. In your opinion, to what extent are **heritage buildings** seen as valuable and attributed a sense of identity and pride within the local **rural** area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not To a very large extent

62. 7. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **rural** area which are now less used due to modern alternatives or industrialisation? *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

63. 8. Are there any **historic construction materials, techniques or styles** in your local **rural** area which have been recently * reintroduced into modern construction?

Local Historic Crafts

This section aims to collect information around traditional crafts within your region. It explores the most common materials and techniques used as well as their unique or distinctive attributes and to what extent these practices have been retained, protected and valued by the local community.

64. 1. What **traditional crafts** were historically practiced within your local area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Carpentry
- Stonemasonry
- Metalwork
- Ceramics and pottery
- Textiles and weaving
- Not sure
- Altele:

65. 2. Are / were there any **traditional crafts** in your local area which you consider distinctive or unique? *

66. 3. To what extent have these **traditional crafts** continued to be practiced within your local area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not To a very large extent

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

67. 4. In which ways to **traditional crafts** play a role in your local area today? *

Select all that apply

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Local economy (e.g craft markets, artisan shops)
- Preservation of cultural heritage (e.g restoration of historic buildings and furniture etc.)
- Tourism (e.g museums, cultural events)
- Education and skills development (e.g workshops, craft schools, apprenticeships)
- Community and social activities (e.g festivals, cultural programs)
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

68. 5. In your opinion, what **challenges exist in preserving the practice of traditional crafts** within your local area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Lack of skilled craftspeople
- Decline in demand for products and services
- Loss of cultural relevance
- Influence of industrial or mass production alternatives
- None
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

69. 6. In your opinion, to what extent are **traditional crafts seen as valuable and attributed a sense of identity and pride** within the local area? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not Very large extent

70. 7. Are there any **traditional craft materials, techniques or styles** in your local area which are now less used due to modern alternatives or industrialisation? *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

71. 8. Are there any **traditional craft materials, techniques or styles** in your local area which have been recently reintroduced? *

72. 9. Are there any **traditional craft materials, techniques or styles** in your local area which you think should be reintroduced? *

73. 10. In your opinion, what challenges could be addressed by preserving or reintroducing the **practice of traditional crafts** within your local area? *

Bifează toate variantele aplicabile.

- Economic (e.g. lack of jobs)
 Technical (e.g. loss of skills and knowledge)
 Political (e.g. lack of support for heritage preservation)
 Cultural (e.g. loss of local/cultural identity)
 Social (e.g. public perception towards craft-based careers)
 Environmental (e.g. waste generation, overuse of unsustainable materials)
 Not sure
 Altele: _____

74. 11. In your opinion, to what extent are **wood traditional crafts seen as valuable and attributed a sense of identity and pride** within the local area ? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not Very large extent

75. 12. In what ways are **traditional wood-related crafts used** today in your city/region ? *

Select all that apply

Marchează un singur oval.

- Still in use
 Being revived
 Underused but valuable
 No longer relevant

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

76. 13. Do you perceive **generational differences in how wood is perceived or valued** in your city or region ? *(such as differences in preferences between older and younger generations regarding the use of wood in buildings)* *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not sure
- Altele: _____

77. 14. Please elaborate / provide further detail if possible. *

78. 15. Can you name any **traditional ways of building with wood or crafts** that were used in your city/region in the past but now have been left ? *

79. 16. Are there any **woodworking techniques, crafts or design styles** you feel are underused but could be addressed in modern contexts ? *

If yes, which ones?

Closing Questions

80. 1. Do you have any additional comments, observations, or suggestions you would like to share ? *

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TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Survey: Local Perceptions of Construction Practices, Wood Use and Crafts

81. 2. Would you like to keep in touch with us ? *

Marchează un singur oval.

- Yes, I would like to subscribe to the newsletter
- Yes, I would be happy to be contacted about optional further involvement (e.g. focussed interviews, stakeholder workshops etc.)
- No, thank you
- Altele: _____

82. 3. If yes, please provide us with your e-mail address (optional) :

Acest conținut nu este nici creat, nici aprobat de Google.

Formulare Google

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